

Agro2Circular

D7.8 – Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Draft)

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Authors: Alba Matamoros (KVC); Aran Blanco (KVC); Mireia Ferri (KVC), Maite Ferrando (KVC), Edoardo Croci (UB), Matteo Donelli (UB), Benedetta Lucchitta (UB), Tania Molteni (UB)

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Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETECK fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
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3 List of abbreviations

CBA	Collective Bargaining Agreement
CE	Circular Economy
EMS	Environmental Management System
ELCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
eLCC	Environmental Life Cycle Costing analysis
KVC	Kveloce I+D+i
LCC	Life Cycle Costing analysis
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LTIFR	Lost Time Injury Frequency Rate
NEP	New Ecological Paradigm
PM	Project Manager
SO-LCA	Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment
TCA	TECNOALIMENTI S.C.P.A.
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme

4 Glossary

Description of the Action: In an H2020 project, the DoA is a document that captures the essence of the envisaged solution in the form of high-level needs and features that gives the reader an overview of the final project deliverable(s). It includes the project work plan and information regarding the project scope, cost, time and risks, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables, and project organisation and approach. The DoA contains the project charter and the project work plan of a PM² project.

Environmental Evaluation (E-LCA). Compilation and evaluation of inputs, outputs, and the potential environmental impacts of a product system through its life cycle and assists in identifying opportunities to improve the environmental performance of products at various points in their life cycle.

Life Cycle Costing Assessment (LCC). Assessment of all costs related to a product or service within its life cycle, from raw material extraction over production and use until disposal.

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). Assessment scheme combining the three life cycle approaches: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) in a common framework to analyse the complete sustainability performance of the product or process system.

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). Methodology to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle, delivering systematic data that can be operationalised through quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods.

Social-Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA). SO-LCA can be understood as a social assessment (SLCA) methodology aimed at evaluating the social aspects of production and their potential positive and negative impacts through their lifecycle, at organisation level.

5 Executive summary <abstract>

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.8 Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis (Draft) and is a summary of the first results of the Agro2Circular project undertaken within task 7.4 Social & economic analysis. This document is complemented by D7.6 Environmental Assessment (Draft) and will be completed by the results of D7.9 Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Final) (M34).

The objective of D7.8 is to provide the first approximation to assess the socioeconomic feasibility of the A2C project and, on the other hand, to estimate the potential impact of the A2C solution considering dimensions at territorial/community level. This screening phase has allowed to pilot the methodologies, indicators and the data gathering procedures established by the evaluation framework (D7.5) for the economic and social dimensions within a realistic environment, representing a "social thermometer" to the action in the organisations representing the different value chains in the Region of Murcia.

Therefore, the aim of D7.8 is to introduce the concept of Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (Section 6), differentiating as a first step the environmental, economic and social dimensions it comprises. Subsequently, the general aim of the deliverable and the screening phase are described, and the scope of the assessment is defined in terms of value chains (section 7). In sections 8 & 9 the goal and scope, the inventory methodology and the data gathering procedures are explained for SO-LCA & LCC respectively. On the one hand the results of the analysis carried out in the social side are presented in section 10, together with the found limitations. On the other hand, the results of the economic side are included in section 11, also together with the limitations. Finally, the main conclusions of the deliverable are included in section 11.

6 Introduction to the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment methodology

In the last decades, environmental challenges related to human activity have arisen, (climate change, depletion of natural resources and raw materials, ecosystem degradation, desertification, air and water pollution, etc.). These challenges must be addressed by society at different levels, from individuals to policy makers and the industry, through the integration of different considerations in decision-making [1]. In this context, *“the importance of adopting a life cycle approach and the development and implementation of policies for resource efficiency, environmentally sound waste management”* was recognized by the United Nations in 2012 [2]. This vision was also embraced through the definition of the Circular Economy (CE) as *“an economy where wastes are recycled into resources, either through a technological feedback mechanism or through a natural ecosystem feedback mechanism, so that the stock of resources is constant or increasing over time”* [3] as opposed to the linear economy, based on the “take-make-dispose” concept [4].

To provide information and allow the assessment of the impacts generated by activities, industrial processes or products, a variety of tools, methodologies and indicators have been developed [5]. The life cycle approach has been claimed since the 1990s, but more actively in use since 2002, through the UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative[6], which is part of the so-called Life Cycle Thinking (LCT), in which the environmental, social, and economic impact of a product is considered over its entire life cycle, including the consumption and end of use phase [7]. The need for a perspective wider than the environmental Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) [8] was formalized into Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework as the combination of the three life cycle approaches: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) in a common framework to analyse the complete sustainability performance of the product or process system [9]. The three dimensions of the LCSA are introduced below.

6.1 Environmental life cycle assessment (LCA)

According to ISO, LCA is *“the compilation and evaluation of inputs, outputs, and the potential environmental impacts of a product system through its life cycle and assists in identifying opportunities to improve the environmental performance of products at various points in their life cycle”* [10]. Modelling the life cycle of a product is based on interlinked unit processes that are connected to each other with material or energy flows. Each process consists of inputs and outputs, which connect the process to previous and following processes. In each process, the burdens imposed on the environment are calculated for the resources and energy consumed (inputs) and the pollutants and wastes emitted (outputs). The inputs and outputs are then assessed for their adverse impacts on renewable and nonrenewable resources, human health, and biodiversity, amongst others[11].

LCA is called “cradle-to-grave” analysis, when it embraces the full life cycle from manufacture (cradle) through the use phase to the disposal phase (grave). On the other hand, “cradle-to-gate” is a partial LCA assessment (from manufacture to the factory gate), omitting the use phase and disposal phase of the product. The rise of recycling technologies has introduced the “Cradle-to-Cradle”[12] analysis as a specific kind of cradle-to-grave assessment, where the end-of-life disposal step for the product is a recycling process.

According to the ISO 14040 standard [10] for life cycle assessment, LCA is an iterative process comprised by four phases, some of which might need to be revised during the calculation process.

- 1- **Goal and scope definition:** this phase describes the study's objective, purpose and audience, sets the system boundaries and the functional units and lists the assumptions and possible scenarios needed in the calculation
- 2- **Life cycle inventory (LCI)** includes the data collection and a balance calculation to all unit processes in the life cycle. The results of LCI are presented as inputs and outputs of the entire system.
- 3- **Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)** converts the LCI results into environmental impacts. There are several impact assessment methods with different optional characterisation, normalisation and weighting factors. The PEF methodology [13] used in the A2C project recommends 16 impact assessment categories.
- 4- **Interpretation of results** is based on all three previous stages of the assessment, being a continuous process in which the consistency of the previous stages is evaluated.

The LCA methodology followed in the A2C project (T7.3) is further detailed in D7.2 (Evaluation Framework), and the results will be explained in D7.6 (Environmental Assessment-Draft, M18) and D7.7 (Environmental Assessment-Final; M34).

6.2 Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA)

Following the definition provided by UNEP Handbook [6], SLCA is “**a methodology to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle**”, delivering systematic data that can be operationalised through quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. The concept arose in the 2000s [26], based on the attempt to build a comprehensive approach to product chains aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's). This insight is deeply connected to the three pillars of sustainability, in which SLCA is supposed to deploy the interplay between industrial processes and social impacts, where the latter are mainly understood as the impacts on human capital, human well-being, cultural heritage and social behaviour [27].

S-LCA has raised the interest of decision makers from several areas, such as investment, business management, industrial management, consumers, NGOs and public policies [28]. For policy-makers, S-LCA could help to design policy measures (i.e taxes) seeking to internalise externalities generated by a type or category of product. For businesses (manufacturers or service providers), S-LCA may serve to gather information for the design and implementation of strategies and actions related to the commitment of their Corporate Social Responsibility strategies; but also to identify possible risks, such as adverse behavioural responses which could potentially undermine a business model. S-LCA is also important for citizens to take individual consumption decisions based on reliable information on how the products or services comply with desirable social norms (i.e fair trade); in the case of NGOs, they may as verifiers, undertaking actions to ensure that these products have

been generated, traded and processed in a way that lessens the negative impacts on sustainable development and boosts the positive ones [27].

Nevertheless, while the performance of an environmental LCA and economic LCC have been set out in detail by ISO standards [10], [19], there are no comparable standards or internationally recognized code of practice for S-LCA. Compared to environmental and economic aspects, social aspects present special challenges because they can be highly diverse and are weighted very differently according to the interest groups and/or countries and regions involved [29], [30]. In addition, the evaluation of social aspects is subjected to a greater variability over time compared to environmental assessment [26], [28], [29].

According to the proposal provided by the UNEP [31] and aligned with the LCA modelling schemes, the main points of the A2C approach towards SLCA are based on both the Methodological Sheets [32] and Reinales et al. [33]. The methodology, framework and indicators were further detailed in D7.2 (Evaluation Framework), and the results will be explained together with the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) in this deliverable and D7.9. But as it will be explained later, the social evaluation goes a step further, considering other indicators to enrich the SO-LCA view. Insights from the SLCA & the other social measurements will also contribute to define the A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool (D7.10) developed in Task 7.5.

6.3 Life Costing assessment (LCC)

LCC can be defined as the assessment of all costs related to a product or service within its life cycle, from raw material extraction over production and use until disposal [8], [14], although, unlike LCA, LCC has been standardized for specific product categories [15], such as water treatment [16], buildings and constructed assets [17] or petroleum and natural gas [18]. The EU has also developed methodologies and tools for LCC in different sectors [19], [20]

An LCC can be performed separating the analysis among the different stakeholders [15] covering all stages from acquisition of the (raw) material, through processing and maintenance, to final disposal or product supply, over a specified time period of interest. The ultimate objective is to compare the (total) life-cycle costs between alternative product or process systems to identify their cost-effectiveness considering all relevant economic factors both in terms of initial costs and future operational costs in their selection and decision-making process when comparing projects for works, goods or services [21]–[23],

The method has evolved over time, since the 1930s: the conventional LCC uses equivalent systems boundaries and same functional units with the environmental life cycle assessment (LCA) explained in the previous section and comprises a complementary assessment; while new LCC variants include an expanded scope, monetizing externalities [19], [23], [24]. Externalities are defined as the consequences of an activity that affects parties other than the organisation undertaking the activity, for which the organisation is neither compensated nor penalised through markets or regulatory mechanisms [25] and must be internalized assigning them a financial value [19]. Externalities can be environmental or non-environmental (which includes social externalities); hence LCC is connected to the LCA and the S-LCA approach.

Besides, the implementation of the LCC is similar to the LCA, based in 3 phases [15].

1. Scoping: Definition of the functional units and system boundaries.

2. Cost modelling: defines the categories of costs, their aggregation, the allocation of costs, and the discounting of future costs. This stage is often divided into two (Cost drivers and data collection, and cost modelling)
3. Evaluation of impacts

The methodology for LCC in the A2C project was further detailed in the Evaluation Framework (D7.2). The Life Cycle Costing Analysis in A2C is performed within Task 7.4 and the results are included in deliverable D7.8 and D7.9 (Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report-Final; M19). Moreover, the findings will contribute to feeding the A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool (D7.10) developed in Task 7.5.

7 Deliverable general aim: SO-LCA & LCC in A2C

7.1 Screening phase of analysis

At this moment, A2C is at the halfway point of its implementation (M18). Although the technological developments are still under development, there are two value chains in which their advancements are at pre-industrial levels. We have chosen to carry out this first exercise of screening in these two value chains, since without enough maturity of the technological advancements, the evaluation would not report consistent results (see next section for more detail on the value chains selection).

Indeed, deliverable 7.8 is considered for the Grant Agreement as a draft version of the socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis. This screening phase has allowed the three scopes (environmental, economic and social) to pilot in a realistic environment the indicators & measurements selected in the evaluation framework and the data gathering procedures. Thus, the results presented in this deliverable are considered as a first step, to the final approach that will be delivered in M34, being them totally exploratory and being considered, on the social side, as a "social thermometer" to the action the different value chains organisations cause in the Region of Murcia.

7.2 Chains selection: rationale

Due to the large amount of the processes involved in the Agro2Circular project at different TRLs and the linkages existing among them, a challenge was found in the definition of the first stage of the SLCA (scope and goals), alongside limitations explained in section 10.2. Limitations. To overcome this issue, two value chains have been selected for the screening stage of the LCSA, the first of them for the agrifood sector and the second for plastics, attending to the following criteria:

1. **TRL Level:** The processes in the value chains selected have reached the industrial or sub-industrial scale. This criteria also responds to the higher costs and resource use in processes in lower TRLs, which may affect the indicators selection, data availability and results of the LCA [34], [35].
2. **Availability of data:** the lack of data across the value chains limits the implementation of circular economy strategies [36]. This criterion is closely related with the previous one, since at early TRLs there is a low availability of data at implementation stage (beyond design/laboratory), as well as a limited number of identified benchmarks with which the developed processes can be compared.
3. **Circularity of processes at the regional level:** the value chains selected have achieved circularity, since they start and end (with upcycled raw material) in the agrifood industry within the region of Murcia. This also responds to the A2C objective of enabling the territorial deployment of the multidimensional solution developed through a demonstrator in the region of Murcia (Spain) integrating the scaled-up technologies, to be later validated and replicated in other territorial contexts.

The two value chains selected are detailed in the following subsections together with the partners involved.

7.2.1 Agrifood value chain

At the screening stage, and according to the previous criteria, the agrifood value chain selected was the **lemon pulp and peels** (Figure 1). The partners involved in this value chain, and therefore contributing to the data collection, are:

- Citromil (CITRO): is a family company founded in 1991, whose main activity is the processing of citrus fruits to be used in different food formulations (juices, drinks, syrups, ice-cream, yoghourts, purees, essential oils, extracts, cloudiness, cells, flavonoids etc) as functional compounds (to reduce acidity, aromatize or texturize in a natural way). The company is committed to sustainable production and will be involved at the implementation of the extraction route, stabilization and validation of bioactive extracts in a real for development of new food formulations.
- Fundación Primafrío (PRIMAFRÍO) is an NGO created as an evolution of the Social Responsibility Strategy of the Primafrío Group, a logistic operator with headquarters in Alhama de Murcia, aiming to provide answers to social, economic, and environmental challenges with innovative proposals. They promote entrepreneurship and the social economy, the sustainable use of natural resources and the prevention of pollution and climate change, by means of R+D+i activities. They will contribute to the waste collection through the community-based initiative performed in T7.1.2.
- Centro Tecnológico de la Conserva (CTNC) is a private non-profit research association of companies, which is recognized by the Spanish Government as Innovation and Technological Centre, Office of Transfer of Research Results and it is declared of Public Use. CTNC works in all fields of the food sector: from agriculture to final processed projects taking into account containers, natural ingredients, valorisation of wastes, environmental impact, etc for the creation of new high value products and the compliance with security standards. CTNC leads the research on extraction routes of high value-added substances at laboratory scale and collaborates in most of the stages of the fruit and vegetable waste value chain: the establishment of A2C requirements for food, nutraceuticals and cosmetic formulations assessment and compliance to food/cosmetic standards, characterisation of agrifood wastes and the development of agrifood waste management plans., extracts purification and evaluation of extracts, design and implementation of the pilot plant for green extraction and the integration of the developed technology at pilot scale in the final A2C demonstrator.
- Mocitos (MCTS) was founded within the Marín Montejano Group in 1986 for the production of juices and drinks in glass and brick containers, and has expanded to cover the packaging of dairy products, wine and derivatives, water, gazpacho, jams and other fruit and vegetable preparations, aseptic production lines of fruit preparations for industrial use and citrus juice extraction. They also work as co-packers for different companies in the food sector. They will collaborate in the development of new formulations with extracts from agri-food and the validation at pilot scale.
- LOLO BIOCOSMETICS (LOLOBIO) is an SME specialized in the manufacturing and commercialisation of biocosmetic and vegan products, being natural and organic, certified toxic free cosmetics and palm oil free, while supporting fair trade and ethically sourcing its ingredients without child labour or dangerous overseas factory conditions. LOLOBIO collaborates in the definition of the A2C cosmetics requirements and the formulation of new cosmetics at small scale using the extracts, being end-users of the bioactive extracts obtained in this value chain.
- LABORATORIOS ALMOND (ALMOND) was created in 1995 in Librilla (Murcia) with the aim of manufacturing food supplements and 100% vegetable food preparations, commercialized under the brand NATURGREEN. The company offers a wide range of products such as oils,

dressings, sugars, cereals, desserts, and beverages, all of them 100% vegetable and free of most allergens, so they are suitable for people with allergies to milk protein and / or egg, lactose intolerances and / or gluten, They are involved in the development of methodologies for new formulations with extracts from agri-food wastes, providing with agrifood wastes, and collaborating in the classification and conditioning. They will be end users validating the bioactive extracts in a real environment, developing new food formulations.

Figure 1. Agrifood value chain: lemon pulp and peel

In this value chain, the lemon pulps and peels are generated in the food industry, being CITROMIL one of the main producers at the regional level, together with PROEXPORT. These partners collect the lemon wastes (T1.4.1) and send them to CTNC; besides, PRIMAFRIO provides an additional smaller amount as a result of the community based scheme (T7.1.2). The waste is transported by CTNC to their facilities in Molina de Segura, where they undergo a mechanical pretreatment for conditioning (T2.1), and subsequently sent to green extraction routes (T2.2)

where high value-added substances (such as carotenoids and phenolic compounds, nutritional fibers) are obtained at laboratory scale. The high value compounds extracted are purified, liofilised and stabilised for conservation at CTNC (T2.3). The extracts are then evaluated for the elaboration of different formulations, in such a way that they can be used by the partners in the agrifood/cosmetic industry in their products (food formulations by MCT and CITRO, nutraceutical formulations by ALMOND and cosmetic formulations by LOLOBIO).

7.2.2 Plastic

In a similar way to the described for the lemon waste, the value chain selected for plastic at the screening stage of this analysis corresponds to the **disinfection film** (Figure 2). The partners that are involved in this value chain, and thus providing with data for the SLCA are:

- PROEXPORT, the Association of Producers-Exporters of Fruits and Vegetables in the Region of Murcia represents companies that are extensive users of agricultural films and packaging, and will collect and provide the plastic waste that will be upcycled in this value chain (gathered and transported by authorized managers as part of their Corporate Social

Figure 2. Disinfection film value chain

- Responsibility); besides, they will be end users of the agri-food debris-based plastics developed in A2C.
- FERROLIVA (<http://www.ferroliva.com>) is an external stakeholder, founded in 1995 in Águilas (Murcia) as a car dismantling company. Their activity has expanded to the collection and management of scrap metal and other types of waste, for the reincorporation to value chains, offering their activities as authorized waste manager in a wide number of businesses of the agrifood sector in the Region of Murcia and the neighbouring province of Almeria (Andalusia). In the particular case of plastic waste (including agricultural plastic), this division of Ferroliva has been integrated in GWC.
 - Green World Compounding (GWC) is an SME based in Alhama de Murcia, producing sustainable compounds and masterbatches from agricultural and industrial plastic waste. GWC is specialized in the manufacturing of recycled products based on polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE) and the leading company of recycled plastics from agricultural and industrial waste sources at the national level. They are involved in the development of methodologies for plastics food contact assessment & compliance to agriculture standards (T1.2), leading the management of plastic waste, pretreatment and contamination, and will manage the integration at pilot scale.
 - SOLPLAST is the division of agricultural plastics of Armando Álvarez Group, funded in 1986 and representing a strong national leader with high production levels. They produce a wide range of plastics with dimensions, mechanical and barrier characteristics adapted to the different demands, among them barrier agriculture films as alternative to current multilayers as well as biodegradable mulch films, for which they test different applications and additives. SOLPLAST acts therefore as an intermediary between GWC and the final users (PROEXPORT) since they are involved in the plastic compounds transformation at laboratory and industrial scale.

In the plastic value chain selected for the screening, the multilayer plastics, known as Totally Impermeable Films (TIF) used for soil disinfection by agricultural companies will be collected and stored by authorized waste managers as required by the national and regional waste regulations, such as FERROLIVA.

The TIF films will be transported to GWC facilities to be characterised (T1.4.2) and subsequently cleaned and decontaminated (T3.1).

Thereafter, GWC will proceed to the mechanical separation of the multilayer films (T3.5) and disgregation into plastic pieces (grinding); these will be the materials that will be extruded to generate new barrier films to gases (T5.4). The barrier plastics will be tested by the end users members of PROEXPORT. This value chain will be integrated in the demonstrator 9 (T6 .1) at industrial scale.

8 Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment

S-LCA can be understood as a social assessment methodology aimed to evaluate the social aspects of production and their potential positive and negative impacts through their lifecycle [7]. The SLCA can be implemented at product level or at organisation level. The table below shows the main differences between both scopes:

Table 1. Overview on differences between S-LCA and SO-LCA & challenges

Phase	S-LCA	SO-LCA
Goal and scope	Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessing social impacts of products. Scope: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products & services. Definition of functional unit. 	Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessing social impacts of organizations. Scope: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizations or parts of organizations Definition of reference unit – the reporting organization – instead of a functional unit.
Inventory	Data needed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Product specific (for different kinds of data used in S-LCA see Section 4.1). Challenge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data on product level may be difficult to obtain. 	Data needed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization specific. Challenge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from organizations still leave challenges on data for stakeholder groups beyond workers.

Source: UNEP guidelines

It is important to remember as stated in section 6.3, that while LCA is a well-established methodology, regulated by the ISO 14040 series of standards, and used in a wide variety of applications, S-LCA/SO-LCA are still in a methodological consolidation phase [37].

For this study, the social evaluation will be focused on the organisation, following the approach so-called Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA). This approach is grounded on the key role of organisations in the transition towards sustainability and CE [38]. Recent literature provides several contributions and case studies to this methodology [39], [40], but the main conclusion is the difficulty in identifying social indicators at the product level as social impacts usually occur at the organisational level. Moreover, Agro2Circular project is not based uniquely on one product, but on a compilation of innovations on Circular Economy. Therefore, the selected unit of analysis has been the organisation instead of the product.

SO-LCA measures social indicators at the organisational level in order to assess the organisation's social performance, hence going beyond the product perspective but considering the organisation as a whole [31]. Furthermore, it also addresses some challenges of the S-LCA, such as the difficulty to link social indicators and impacts to the product level by means of the functional unit (see 10.2. Limitations chapter for more detail).

8.1 Goal and Scope

The overall goal of this study (SO-LCA) is to analyse the performance of the organisations in order to promote the improvement of social conditions and/or their contribution to the social development of each organisations' stakeholder. In this first screening stage, the organisations analysed have been selected due to their involvement in the most mature value chains of the project (please see chapter 7.2. *Chains selection: rationale* for more

detail on the product chains selection criteria). The selected organisations belong to the agrifood (lemon pulp and peels) value chain and plastic value chain (disinfection film), as listed below:

- Agrifood value chain: CTNC, MCTS, CITROMIL, PRIMAFRIO, ALMOND, LOLOBIO.
- Plastic value chain: PROEXP, GWC.

The reporting organisation was chosen as the unit of analysis by setting the boundaries of the system “*from cradle to gate*”, in accordance with the UNEP guidelines for SO-LCA [31]. It also needs to be mentioned that, due to the nature of the analysis itself, the SO-LCA is going to be carried out within the value chains in an aggregated way, not considering the organisations individually. Also, the results must be considered carefully due to the heterogeneity of the organisations.

The SO-LCA calls upon a stakeholder approach where the potential impacts on different stakeholder categories are considered. This mirrors the fact that social sustainability is about identifying and managing impacts, both positive and negative, on people (stakeholders). Social impacts are classified by stakeholder categories to assist with the operationalization and to ensure the comprehensiveness of the results [31]. The quality of an organisation’s relationships and engagement with its stakeholders is critical for its social performance. In this study, the stakeholders’ categories included in the UNEP guidelines are considered as well as several of their corresponding impact subcategories (see Table 2). Concretely the selected stakeholders’ categories have been workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers. The guidelines allow for customization of stakeholder selection criteria and for defining the most appropriate impact categories for social assessment. Thus, the children stakeholder category has been excluded as this method aims to use organisation-specific social metrics and primary data only, the choice of key stakeholders must represent the real value chain; therefore, this category was considered irrelevant to the sectorial dimensions of the value chain of the organisations undergoing the assessment. In the table below, the selected stakeholders and the impact subcategories analysed for all the organisations are presented.

Table 2. Stakeholder category & impact subcategories

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategories
Workers	Forced labour
	Fair salary
	Working hours
	Equal opportunities/ discrimination
	Health and safety
	Social benefits, legal issues
	Workers’ rights
	Sexual harassment
Value chain actors	Fair competition
	Promoting social responsibility
	Supplier relationships
	Respect of intellectual property rights
	Wealth distribution
Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues
	Contribution to economic development

	Technology development
	Corruption
	Poverty alleviation
Local community	Access to material resources
	Access to immaterial resources
	Delocalization and migration
	Cultural heritage
	Safe and healthy living conditions
	Community engagement
	Local employment
	Secure living conditions
Consumers	Health and Safety
	Feedback mechanism
	Consumer privacy
	Transparency
	End-of-life responsibility

Source: adapted from the UNEP guidelines. For further details go to Annex I: 14.1 Social Indicators Battery

For each impact subcategory several indicators were defined in order to represent as fully as possible the organisations' value chains with data coming from primary sources (see 8.2. Inventory).

Beyond the SO-LCA approach detailed above, the authors considered that additional social elements would enrich the analysis. A2C projects proposes a systemic solution to circular economy in the agrifood sector, with a strong focus on public engagement, which means that the four stakeholder groups supporting innovation processes are strongly involved in the projects activities (Public Administration, Industry, Research and technology institutions and Citizens). SO-LCA is a useful tool to assess the organisations' social conditions and to understand if the product value chains selected (in which the developed technology is being tested) contributes to the social development of each stakeholder around these organisations. However, A2C goes beyond the organisations themselves, promoting a more multi-level approach, relying on achieving in the long term a change of paradigm, rational innovation and social inclusion & scale-up the project innovations, including the social outcomes. Hence, beyond the SO-LCA itself, several measurements related with environmental awareness, sustainability & circular economy concepts have also been included in the analysis for exploratory purposes. We consider that A2C activities have the potential to assess specific constructs that can support the adoption of circular economy, such as the attitudes towards the environment and the nature, the need of reducing food and plastic waste, the acceptance of more sustainable and circular products as part of our consumers preferences, to mention some. Since the scope of the SO-LCA is much focused on economic/demographic/legal (human rights) aspects, leaving out key socio-psychological elements for ecological and sustainable behaviour change which are also targeted by A2C project.

Therefore, in this first screening phase it has been decided to conceptually broaden the social dimensions of the SO-LCA with the variables that are presented in the following table:

Table 3. Workers awareness on sustainability & circular economy measurements

NEP (New ecological paradigm) [41]	Limits to growth, anti-anthropocentrism, the fragility of nature's balance, rejection of human exemptionalism, possibility of an ecocrisis
Consumers awareness [42]	Recycling attitudes and knowledge
Consumers desire [42]	Plastic recycling attitudes & authorities' role
Circular economy awareness [43]	Circular economy behaviours
	Circular economy acknowledgement
	Perception of quality according to type of product
	Sustainable practices
	Behavioural shifts

To summarize, although the selected methodology a priori to perform the analysis on task 7.4. was the S-LCA together with the LCC, more indicators to assess the workers awareness and acceptance were included in the social evaluation, even if they were not envisaged in the framework (D7.5), due to the fact that the S-LCA approach is too narrow for the project scope. These additional indicators will enrich the analysis at the organisational level by adding a more person-based perspective to the managerial and stakeholder point of view. Moreover, the inclusion of these indicators is justified to overcome some of the methodological limitations presented on the sections below.

In both cases, the procedure for data collection involves the use of primary data compiled through different data tools, namely questionnaires designed exclusively for this project and presented in the following chapters (10. *SO-LCA implementation* (preliminary)).

8.2 Inventory & procedure methodology

The first step in inventory analysis is to identify the social metrics through which conduct the social assessment. The data is required to be specific and characteristic of the studied organisations. Moreover, it must also be directly and easily measurable in order to have primary data as set by the established goal of the evaluation.

The criteria to choose the metrics for this first screening stage were mainly based on the UNEP guidelines and on the results of fuzzy Delphi study carried out by A. Padilla-Rivera, B.B.T. do Carmo, G. Arcese et al [44]. Bibliographic research was also conducted reviewing the most recent articles related with the selection of SO-LCA indicators [45], [46]. Thus, we have chosen the metrics that meet the methodological requirements set in the evaluation framework (relevance, measurability, reliability, timeliness, comparability, clarity and availability), and we have correlated them with the stakeholders and social *impact* categories. Moreover, and following the UNEP guidelines for SO-LCA and the scholars' proposals, site specific indicators were associated with the impact subcategories and SDG as shown in Table 4. The stakeholder category **WORKERS** corresponds to eight impact subcategories aimed to assess:

- whether the organisation doesn't use forced or compulsory labour;
- whether practices concerning wages are in compliance with established standards and if the wage provided is meeting legal requirements;

- if the number of hours effectively worked is in accordance with the ILO standards and when overtime occurs, compensation is planned and provided to the workers, in terms of money or free time;
- how equal opportunity practices are managed and the presence of discrimination in the opportunities offered to the workers;
- the rate of incidents and the status of prevention measures and management practices in the organisation;
- whether and to what extent an organisation provides social benefits and social security to workers;
- the compliance of the organisation with freedom of association and collective bargaining standards and
- whether an organisation might create or tolerate working conditions in which sexual harassment occurs, and to what extent company actions are successful in preventing sexual harassment.

To assess this stakeholder category 16 indicators were defined following, in some cases, the definitions established in the D.7.5. Evaluation Framework and methodology. The new indicators definition has been established following the UNEP Methodological sheets [47] and the study carried out by F. García-Muiña, M.S. Medina-Salgado and R. González-Sánchez et al. [37]. Moreover, and considering the methodological limitations (see 10.2. Limitations), also several indicators have been included or modified taking into account the criteria of experts at KVC and UVEG¹.

Regarding the associated sustainable development goals[48], the only non-related SGD are: 7 (*affordable and clean energy*), 12 (*responsible consumption & production*), 13 (*climate action*), 14 (*life below water*), 15 (*life on land*), 16 (*peace, justice & strong institutions*) & 17 (*partnership for the goals*).

The second stakeholder category is **VALUE CHAIN**, to which five impact subcategories correspond. This impact subcategories were aimed to:

- assess if the organisation's competitive activities are conducted in a fair way and in compliance with legislations preventing anti-competitive behaviour, anti-trust, or monopoly practices;
- assess whether the enterprise promotes social responsibility among its suppliers and through its own actions;
- evaluate if the organisation considers the potential impacts or unintended consequences of its procurement and purchasing decisions on other organisations, and act with due diligence to avoid or minimize any negative impact (ISO 26000);
- check whether organisation's actions safeguard and value the creators and other producers of intellectual goods and services and
- evaluate the extent to which the value is distributed in an equitable way to all the actors of the value chain.

To assess this stakeholder category 7 indicators were defined. Due to the nature of this stakeholder category and the associated impact types, just 5 SGD are related to them: 1 (*no poverty*), 8 (*decent work and economic growth*), 9 (*industry, innovation and infrastructure*), 10 (*reduce inequalities*) & 12 (*responsible consumption and production*).

¹ This case concrete of workers stakeholder category is extendable to all the indicators included in each impact subcategory. The initial list of indicators included in the evaluation framework has been modified considering the evaluation scope.

SOCIETY has also been considered. Within this stakeholder category, five impact subcategories were analysed, aiming to:

- assess to what extent the selected organisations are engaged in reducing its sustainability impacts;
- assess to what extent the organisation/product or service contributes to the economic development of the society;
- assess whether the organisation participates in joint research and development for efficient and environmental sound technologies;
- evaluate if an organisation has implemented appropriate measures to prevent corruption and if there is evidence that it has engaged or has been engaged in corruption and
- to measure the presence or not of proactive activities, such as strategies, action plans, investment, to reduce the poverty of the society at different geographical levels made by the organisation itself or linked with the product life cycle.

There are seven established indicators corresponding to this stakeholder category, aligned with nine SDGs: 1 (*no poverty*), 2 (*zero hunger*), 3 (*good health and well-being*), 4 (*quality education*), 8 (*decent work and economic growth*), 9 (*industry, innovation and infrastructure*), 12 (*responsible consumption and production*), 16 (*peace, justice and strong institutions*) & 17 (*partnership for the goals*).

LOCAL COMMUNITY, configured by eight impact categories, has also been considered as a stakeholder category due to the configuration of the A2C model (regional based) and the importance of the agrifood industry in the region of Murcia. The aim of the selected impact categories is to:

- assess the extent to which organisations respect, work to protect, to provide or to improve community access to local material resources, infrastructures & immaterial resources;
- evaluate whether organisations contribute to delocalization, migration, or “involuntary resettlement” within communities and whether populations are treated adequately;
- check whether an organisation respects local cultural heritage and recognizes that all community members have a right to pursue their cultural development;
- assess how organisations impact community safety and health;
- appraise whether an organisation includes community stakeholders in relevant decision-making processes. It also considers the extent to which the organisation engages with the community as a whole;
- assess the role of an organisation in directly or indirectly affecting local employment &
- evaluate how organisations impact the security of local communities with respect to the conduct of private security personnel and how the organisation interacts with state-led forces.

Eleven indicators were defined for this category, being the stakeholder category with more metrics following workers. As for the SDG, the ones corresponding to this category are: 3 (*good health and well-being*), 4 (*quality education*), 6 (*clean water and sanitation*), 8 (*decent work and economic growth*), 9 (*industry, innovation and infrastructure*), 10 (*reduce inequalities*), 11 (*sustainable cities and communities*), 12 (*responsible consumption and production*) & 16 (*peace, justice and strong institutions*).

The last considered stakeholder category is **CONSUMERS**. This category is built up by 5 impact categories to assess how the organisations relate with their customers, concretely it is sought to:

- identify the existence and scope of systematic efforts to address consumer health and safety across the organisations involved in the life cycle of a product and/ or service;

- assess the effectiveness of management measures to support consumer feedback. In addition, this subcategory may assess other management practices related to customer feedback;
- examine whether organisational management systems work to respect and protect consumer privacy;
- assess if the organisation communicates on all issues regarding its product and social responsibility in a transparent way &
- evaluate if there exist (if applicable) any management efforts to address the social impacts of product or service end-of-life.

Within this category, seven indicators were defined. As for the SDG the following ones are related with the selected impact subcategories: 2 (*zero hunger*), 3 (*good health and well-being*), 8 (*decent work and economic growth*), 9 (*industry, innovation and infrastructure*), 12 (*responsible consumption and production*), 15 (*life on land*) & 16 (*peace, justice and strong institutions*).

Below a summary table can be found where the relations between the stakeholders' categories, impact subcategories, indicators and SDG are shown.

Table 4. List of stakeholder categories, impact subcategories, indicators and related SDGs

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	Indicators	Related SDGs
WORKERS	Forced labour	- Employment terms - Forced Labour	SDG 3 SDG 8 SDG 10
	Fair salary	- Living wage per month - Minimum wage, per month - Organisation average wage, per month	SDG 1 SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 4
	Working hours	- Flexibility - Full-time staff	SDG 3 SDG 8
	Equal opportunities/ discrimination	- Gender equality - Equal opportunities policies	SDG 1 SDG 4 SDG 5 SDG 8 SDG 10
	Health and Safety	- Occupational safety measures - Lost time injury frequency rate - Presence of sufficient safety measures	SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 6 SDG 8
	Social benefits, legal issues	- Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	SDG 3 SDG 8 SDG 9 SDG 11
	Workers' rights	- Trade unions density - Collective Bargaining Agreement	SDG 8 SDG 10 SDG 16
	Sexual harassment	- Sexual harassment incidents reported	SDG 8
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	Fair competition	- Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	SDG 12
	Promoting social responsibility	- Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility - Suppliers audit	SDG 12
	Supplier relationships	- Suppliers' communication relationship	SDG 12
	Respect of intellectual property rights	- Use of local intellectual property	SDG 9
	Wealth distribution	- Fair price definition	SDG 1 SDG 8 SDG 10
SOCIETY	Public commitment to sustainability issues	- Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	SDG 12 SDG 17
	Contribution to economic development	- Total taxation per capita	SDG 1 SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 4 SDG 8 SDG 9
	Technology development	- Technology transfer - Investments in technology development/ transfer	SDG 4 SDG 9 SDG 17
	Corruption	- Corruption	SDG 16

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	Indicators	Related SDGs
LOCAL COMMUNITY	Poverty alleviation	- Poverty alleviation programme	SDG 1 SDG 2
	Access to material resources	- Environmental management system	SDG 9 SDG 12
	Access to immaterial resources	- Community education initiatives	SDG 4 SDG 12
	Delocalization and migration	- Immigrant workforce rate - Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	SDG 9 SDG 10 SDG 11
	Cultural heritage	- Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage	SDG 11
	Safe and healthy living conditions	- Promotion of community health	SDG 3 SDG 6
	Community engagement	- Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation - Number of meetings with community stakeholders	SDG 11 SDG 12
	Local employment	- Workforce hired locally - Spending on locally based suppliers	SDG 8
CONSUMERS	Secure living conditions	- Security complaints by the community	SDG 3 SDG 16
	Health and Safety	- Labelling - Consumer complaints - Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 12
	Feedback mechanism	- Presence of consumers feedback mechanism	SDG 12
	Consumer privacy	- Consumers complaints related to breach of privacy	SDG 8 SDG 16
	Transparency	- Organisation communication transparency	SDG 9 SDG 12
	End-of-life responsibility	- Internal management systems	SDG 12 SDG 15

Source: prepared by the authors based on [31], [32], [37]

In order to overcome the methodological restrictions derived from the SO-LCA and to also analyse the workers' awareness and perception regarding CE and sustainability in general, several additional indicators, besides the ones related with the SO-LCA were considered (see 8.1. Goal and Scope).

The “New ecological paradigm” scale [41] has been included due to its robustness and methodological consolidation. The NEP scale became one of the most reliable and widely used measures of environmental concern in the world and has been used in hundreds of empirical studies in dozens of nations [49]. It is composed by fifteen statements where respondents are asked to indicate the strength of their agreement or disagreement, which afterwards is used to construct various statistical measures of environmental concerns. Specifically, the NEP is used for measuring people's environmental attitudes and underlying ecological worldviews. Taking in consideration the characteristics of A2C project the evaluation team decided to consider it as a complement to the SO-LCA.

Indicators regarding consumers awareness and desire on the three R's (reducing, recycling and reuse) were also included, being the same used by the partner TCA in a study carried out in Italy [42]. It was decided to use the same indicators in order to homogenize the data to compare it, if the opportunity arises in the future. The organisations employees were asked to answer these questions as consumers. The queries were centered in recycling, waste separating & the authorities role regarding recycling.

The last group of indicators included are centered in gatering information regarding the workers awarenes related with circular economy. These indicators were obtained from a recent study carried out in the region of Catalonia and in a Scottish region with the aim to analyse the behaviours, attitudes, perceptions and motivations of citizens regarding sustainability and the adoption of circular economy practices [43]. The study is centered in five different industries: food, cosmetics and personal hygiene, perfumery, fashion and energy. Due to the nature of A2C project, the indicators related to the food industry were selected.

8.3 Data gathering

This section objective is to present the data gathering procedure used in the screening phase presented in this deliverable for the social evaluation. In Image 1 all the followed steps are shown. The process can be split up into two main tasks: data collection tools preparation (orange square) and the data collection procedure itself (green square).

Image 1 Screening phase: data gathering procedure

Source: prepared by the authors

8.3.1 Questionnaires design

Two questionnaires were designed differentiating by the stakeholder to whom they were addressed. On the one hand a Project Manager Form was designed for the top management figures of the selected organisations. In this form just questions related with the SO-LCA were included and the tool used to collect the information has been a Word document. The reason why it was designed using Word and no other tool such as Forms or JotForm was because since it's an editable format, managers could include comments. Some of the included questions were to some extent sensible information (i.e. *the organisation average wage in nominal terms, per month*), thus all the facilities were given to the managers to include questions in order to provide the required information.

Firstly, the questions were divided per stakeholder category, according to the categories defined in the inventory (workers, value chain, society, local community & consumers). However, after testing it with one of the designated leaders on the value chains (CETEC) it was decided for the sake of clarity, to redistribute the sections per department (to put together the questions that each department concerned should fill in). Thus, the questions were divided as follows:

- Human resources department, made up of 19 questions;
- Finance & administration department, made up of 16 questions;
- Agreements & special programs, made up of 10 questions;
- Consumers, made up of 6 questions.

All the questions were codified according to the indicator they are associated to.

On the other hand, a worker's questionnaire was also framed. Although SO-LCA questions were also included, this questionnaire was likewise used to include questions about awareness, desire, and CE consciousness to achieve a first sight of the perception of the workers employed in the A2C organisations. Since the number of responses was expected to be higher, this questionnaire was displayed using JotForms. This questionnaire was also tested by KVC's workers. It was structured along the following sections in order to make it an easy friendly tool for users:

- Sociodemographic section, made up of 5 questions;
- SO-LCA section, made up of 4 questions;
- New Ecological Paradigm section, made up of 1 questions;
- Survey on consumers- awareness section, made up of 3 questions;
- Survey on consumers-desire section, made up of 2 questions;
- Circular economy awareness section, made up of 5 questions.

For further details on the indicators please see the annex section: 14.1. Social Indicators Battery.

As for the languages, both questionnaires were designed in English, and then the workers one was translated into Spanish.

In both questionnaires, a confidentiality clause was added in order to guarantee, on the one hand, the exclusive use of the PM Form data in the framework of the A2C project and, on the other hand, the anonymity of the respondents to the employee questionnaire.

Moreover, since this is a first screening exercise, the possibility of updating the questionnaires or including more questions in the final round exists.

8.3.2 Data gathering process

Data gathering is a costing procedure. The partner's collaboration is critical & essential to achieve a good sample result. To ensure a smooth communication and to optimize the procedure, for each value chain a leader was designated. In the case of the plastic value chain is CETEC and for the agrifood value chain is CTNC.

Once the data collection tools were designed, the Project Manager form was validated by one of the value chain leaders (CETEC) in order to assess its usability and understandability. After the validation of the questionnaires, an email was sent to each of the members of the value chains with the Project Manager form attached and the link to the workers questionnaire to be spread up among the employees.

Several meetings with the partners were held and emails were exchanged to finetune what was expected from the questionnaire.

Also, an excel file was created as a data base to dump all the data collected with the PM Forms.

9 Costing Life Cycle assessment

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) is a methodology that entails the systematic economic evaluation of the costs of an asset, product or service throughout its life cycle, covering all stages from acquisition of the raw material, through processing and maintenance, to final disposal or product supply, over a specified time period of interest.

LCC aims at comparing the (total) life-cycle costs between alternative product or process systems to identify their cost-effectiveness considering all relevant economic factors both in terms of initial costs and future operational costs. This methodology is particularly effective whenever products have a long lifetime and/or high maintenance, use or disposal costs. This technique enables comparative cost assessments to be made over a specified period of time, taking into account all relevant economic factors both in terms of initial costs and future operational costs.

An LCC analysis summarizes all costs associated with the life cycle of a product that are directly covered by one or more actors in the product life cycle (for example, suppliers, producers, users or consumers, end-of-life managers).

LCC has been widely used by both decision-makers and businesses, in order to identify the impact of products and services in terms of costs in a life span or life cycle perspective and to select the best alternatives. One of the main fields of application of LCC proved to be among products or investments requiring high initial capital, such as buildings, infrastructures and durable goods in general, with the different perspective of the producer, the owner or the user/consumer. In fact, an international standard for LCC has been developed only for the building sector [17], while for other product categories no standardization occurred so far. Besides the before mentioned sectorial ISO standard, several guidelines for LCC methodologies, some of them being mostly framework references, have been produced (i.e., [17], [50]–[53] and other Standard Practice for Life Cycle Cost Analysis of certain products published by ASTM).

With reference to the food sector, LCC is explicitly mentioned in the EU policy guideline on Public Procurement², with specific reference to catering services. In particular, the main topic reported with a LCC perspective is the life cycle cost of refrigerators and freezers, which can be a relevant hotspot for both environmental and costing impacts of food, while food or food waste are not addressed.

Among the approaches that can be found in the literature, mainly differing in terms of perspective, cost categories included, and potential application, 3 types of LCC methodologies emerged [54]:

- Conventional LCC (cLCC)
- Environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC)
- Societal Life Cycle Costing (sLCC)

² Article 68(2) of Directive 2014/24/EU and Article 83(2) of Directive 2014/25/EU

Figure 3 Different types of Life Cycle Costing [55]

Conventional LCC (C-LCC) techniques are usually applied in the context of decisions on products or investments requiring high initial capital. C-LCC assesses the total cost performance of an asset over time, including the acquisition, operating, maintenance, and end-of-life costs. Its primary use concerns the evaluation of different options for achieving the client’s objectives, as the alternatives differ not only in their initial costs, but also in their subsequent operational costs. LCC techniques can be equally applied to *major constructed assets or to the individual components and materials* from which they are constructed [56]. C-LCC can be addressed as a discounted cash flow analysis, therefore used to evaluate large investments, such as new food processing plants or machineries, where the costs occurring throughout the entire lifespan of these durable goods can then be attributed to single products based on yield or other allocation criteria.

Depending on what the object and the purpose of the assessment are, the relevant costs to be included could vary. For instance, in the case of buildings, energy consumption costs across the whole life-time of the asset can constitute an important share of overall costs, whereas, for other facilities, the bulk of costs might occur largely during the initial phases of the project development.

Consequently, cost’s categories to include are one of the key parameters to identify during the process. As an alternative to traditional accounting, LCC can provide valuable information on the dimension and structure of costs potentially incurred by new processes or products already during their development phase [57].

Within the C-LCC perspective, typically dealing with products or services with a relatively high lifespan, all the costs are discounted to take into proper consideration the impact of time within the cashflow of the system analysed.

A broader concept of Life Cycle Costing, considering the environmental externalities, is often referred to as Environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC); eLCC was developed to support environmental life cycle assessment (LCA): it covers the economic dimension and helps identify hotspots in both cost and environmental impacts. This technique was designed to include in the assessment all those costs occurring during the life cycle of products, services, and technologies.

eLCC is, in fact, aligned with ELCA (Environmental LCA), and follows the same phases included in the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards ([10], [58]):

1. Goal and scope definition
2. Data collection
3. Impact assessment
4. Interpretation and sensitivity analysis

The approach relies on the same basic life cycle perspective of the LCA and its output. Environmental impacts associated to each life cycle phase will be monetized according to specific methodologies, and added to conventional costs that occur during the full life cycle of a product/process. **This will be the approach used within the A2C project**

Finally, the inclusion of costs covered by anyone in society further enlarges the LCC perspective, leading to Societal Life Cycle Costing (sLCC), which aims at assessing the overall direct and indirect costs covered by the society in the long-term. sLCC can be applied by policy makers to better identify larger effects and indirect cost of production systems and their alternatives, since all the stakeholders and the overall society is included in the assessment.

The application of LCC for food products and food waste streams seems to be recent and minimal, if compared to other sectors.

9.1 Goal and Scope

Within the Agro2Circular Project, the aim of this phase is to compare the associated economic and environmental costs (eLCC) over the entire life cycle of the innovative solutions which will be tested, in comparison with the Business as usual (BAU) solution.

Two specific case studies will be analysed:

- Extraction of fibres and polyphenol from lemon waste (peel/pulp)
- Agricultural film with recycled content material

The 2 above mentioned innovative processes will be compared against their relevant traditional solutions, as it is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. A2C Projects and conventional solution for comparison

Innovative process within the Agro2Circular Project	Conventional solution
Extraction of fibres and polyphenol from lemon waste (peel/pulp)	Fibres already available in the market (i.e. organic inulin, pectin, organic psyllium, quercetin)
Agricultural film with recycled content material	Agricultural film with no recycled content material

In Agro2Circular Project, the eLCC will consider both conventional costs and the monetization of environmental externalities evaluated in the LCA. The following image synthesises the main cost categories that will be considered.

A2C LCC approach

Figure 4. Structure of the eLCC in Agro2Circular Project

9.1.1 Functional/declared unit.

One of the key elements to be defined in any Life Cycle assessment is the definition of the so-called functional unit. The functional unit is the quantified performance of a product system, to be used as a reference unit. It is a measure of the function of the studied system and it provides a reference to which the inputs and outputs can be related, thus enabling comparison of alternative systems. The functional unit will be used as a common reference to report the results of the assessment.

The functional unit is a key element of LCA which must be clearly defined since it is a quantified description of the performance requirements that the product system fulfills: besides the function, it comprises a quantity, a duration and a level of quality. Some considerations pertain to eLCC. In the case of waste systems and food waste, functional units are generally based on mass (i.e. 1 kg of recycled product) and, whenever an eLCC is performed, they are coherent with the LCA.

Whenever the function of the studied product is not precisely defined, for instance in case of ingredients of materials that can be used in different types of products or for different applications, or when the system boundaries do not cover a full life cycle (i.e. “cradle-to-gate approach³”), a declared unit is used instead of a functional unit.

Within the Agro2Circular Project, a declared unit will be used, in tight connection with the LCA study. Table 6 shows the declared unit that will be used in the eLCC comparison.

Table 6- Declared units for eLCC comparison

Innovative process within the Agro2Circular Project	Conventional solution	Declared unit
Extraction of fibres and polyphenol from lemon waste (peel/pulp)	Fibres already available in the market (i.e. organic inulin, pectin, organic psyllium, quercetin)	1 kg of fibres

³ Under a cradle-to-gate approach the boundaries of the life cycle assessment are set to analyse the activity from the extraction of raw materials until the gate at the production facility.

Agricultural film with recycled content material	Agricultural film with no recycled content material	1 kg of agricultural film
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9.1.2 System boundaries

Cradle-to-gate approaches scenarios will be developed in order to compare the costs of the innovative solutions against the conventional ones. The rationale for the selection of system boundaries has been explained in section 7.2.

With reference to the lemon waste demo case, the following life cycle phases will be included in the eLCC assessment (see Figure 1):

- lemon waste collection (peel/pulp)
- lemon waste transport to the recycling facility
- mechanical pretreatment
- extraction (green solvents)
- lyophilisation and stabilisation
- formulation development (food, nutraceuticals, etc.)

With reference to the agricultural film demo case, the following life cycle phases will be included in the eLCC assessment (Figure 2):

- agricultural film waste collection
- agricultural film waste transport to the recycling facility
- cleaning, decontamination and mechanical recycling

9.2 Inventory & procedure methodology

In order to include the environmental externalities, the eLCC assessment will follow the same structure of the LCA. Cost data will be obtained mainly from the real case studies (primary data). When primary cost data could not be obtained, average figures from the technical literature will be used.

The following cost categories will be included in the study:

- **Raw material costs**, including:
 - a. the acquisition of waste stream input needed to manufacture the products in the recycling process,
 - b. the extraction and processing of auxiliaries raw materials needed to manufacture the products in the recycling process
- **Transport costs** to the manufacturing plant: cost of freight, cartage, transit insurance and cost of operating fleet and other incidental charges
- **Equipment costs**: the total purchase cost associated with the equipment necessary to set up the process. The item will consider the yearly price over the expected life of the asset.
- **Installation costs**: the total cost of installing the systems and equipment, in case not already available to the manufacturer.
- **Labour costs**: the cost of the needed man-hours associated with upcycling processes and with the treatment of wastes.

- **Energy consumption costs:** the total energy consumption cost for the facility and systems. It includes the cost of fuel required to generate power
- **Water consumption costs:** the total water consumption cost for the facility and systems.
- **Maintenance costs:** the total cost incurred to maintain the capacity of performance of the facility and equipment
- **Waste management costs:** the total cost incurred to manage waste emerging during the recycling process.

9.3 Data gathering

As previously mentioned, cost data will be gathered mainly from the real case studies (primary data), by means of questionnaires specifically designed by Bocconi University in tight cooperation with the partners responsible for the demo cases. The next figure shows an example of such eLCC data collection questionnaires.

Stage: Collection and transport				
Cost category: Transport costs				
<i>Please provide an estimation of transport costs for lemon waste used in the circular process:</i>				
Transport service	Service cost (€)	Service cost per ton of waste	Notes	
Stage: Mechanical pretreatment				
Cost category: Equipment and material purchase costs				
<i>Is new equipment used for the mechanical pretreatment process?</i>				
Y/N				
<i>If yes, please provide the related information below:</i>				
Equipment name	Equipment purchase cost (€)	Expected equipment life (n.of year)	Capacity (in tons)	Notes
<i>Is existing equipment used for the mechanical pretreatment process?</i>				
Y/N				
<i>If existing equipment is used, please provide the annual amortization costs:</i>				
Equipment name	Equipment annual amortization cost (€)	Notes		
<i>Are materials used in the mechanical pretreatment process?</i>				
Y/N				
<i>If yes, please provide the information below:</i>				
Material name	Amount of material used for treatment of 1 ton of lemon waste	Unit	Cost per unit (€)	Notes

Figure 5. Example of eLCC data collection questionnaire

When primary cost data could not be obtained, average figures from the technical literature were used.

9.3.1 Data and assumptions

Service Life of the product

In LCC, the expected life of an asset or a product has a huge impact on the life cycle analysis, since all the costs occurring in its lifespan should be taken into account. For the building sector, for example, the service life refers to the period of time during which a building or its components satisfy the minimum acceptable level of performance [59] and the International standard ISO 15686–5:2008 [17] recommends that the estimated service life of a building should not be less than its design life.

In Agro2Circular Project, the eLCC of the 2 solutions that will be analysed, will consider a service life within one year, given the type of products that will be obtained through the recycling process.

Period of analysis

The period of analysis refers to the time horizon over which the life cycle cost is analysed. In its origin, life cycle costing does not necessarily cover the whole life cycle of a product, system, or an asset. The aforementioned international standard ISO 15686–5:2008 [17] for buildings recommends not to exceed 100 years.

The residual value of the asset/product analysed is the product value remaining at the end of the study period. In the construction sector, for example (Building for Environmental and Economic Sustainability -BEES model [60]) the residual value is computed by prorating the purchase and installation cost over the product life remaining beyond the 50-year period.

In Agro2Circular Project, the analysis will cover the same period of analysis of the service life.

Discount rate

Discount rate is used to convert costs occurring at different times to equivalent costs at a common point in time [61]. The most common technique of making incoming and outgoing payments from different times comparable is to apply a discount to future payments to obtain a Net Present Value (NPV).

As the life cycle costs are discounted to their present value, selection of a suitable discount rate is a crucial decision in a LCC. The International Standard ISO 15686–5:2008 [17] recommends that the determined discount rate, for private sector projects, should cover the opportunity cost of the invested capital which can be:

- a. the interest cost of a loan for investment,
- b. the interest lost from cash reductions from deposits,
- c. the lost return from other possible investment,
- d. the actual return from capital investments
- e. the anticipated rate of return from the new business.

For public sector projects, the International Standard recommends using the discount rate which is determined by the central government.

Future costs must be expressed in terms that are consistent with the discount rate used. Two approaches are usually applied. First, a real discount rate may be used with constant-dollar costs. Real discount rates reflect that portion of the time value of money attributable to the real earning power of money over time and not to general price inflation. Second, a market discount rate may be used with current-dollar amounts (e.g. actual future prices). Market discount rates reflect the time value of money stemming from both inflation and the real earning power of money over time (bees)

In Agro2Circular Project, since the period of analysis does not exceed one year, the discount rate will not have impact on the analysis.

Inflation rate

General price inflation is the reduction in the purchasing power of the money from year to year, as measured, for example, by the percent increase in the Gross National Product (GNP) deflator over a given year. In Agro2Circular Project, since the period of analysis does not exceed one year, the inflation rate will not be considered.

Environmental externalities

Environmental externalities refer to the economic concept of uncompensated environmental effects of production and consumption that affect consumer utility and enterprise cost, outside the market mechanism.

As a consequence of negative externalities, private costs of production tend to be lower than their “social” costs. It is the aim of the “polluter/user-pays” principle to prompt households and enterprises to internalise externalities in their plans and budgets.

In Agro2Circular Project, externalities will be calculated using the “Environmental Prices” concept [62]. Environmental Prices is a method developed by CE Delft for expressing environmental impacts in monetary unit and a measure to express the amount of environmental burden of a product on the basis of prevention of that burden. Those are the costs which should be born to reduce the environmental pollution and materials depletion in our world to a level which is in line with the carrying capacity of our planet. The method, developed by the Delft University of Technology, has the advantage that the output of the LCA is expressed in a monetary value (€).

The output of the LCA studies on the 2 demo cases will be used to monetize the environmental impacts.

10 SO-LCA implementation (preliminary)

10.1 Results per stakeholder category

The main results per stakeholder category of this first phase of analysis are shown below. As explained in section 8 (Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment), the data come mainly from two sources: the project managers which reported the organisation information and the employees of the value chain organisations.

Before starting with the analysis of results, we need to scale them by value chain.

Table 7. Value chains sample size & heterogeneity (SO-LCA)

	Value chain 1: agrifood (lemon pulp and peels)	Value chain 2: plastic (disinfection film)
<i>Number of organisations</i>	6	2
<i>Sample size of employees who answered the questionnaire</i>	81	2
<i>Reference years</i>	2021-2022	2021-2022
<i>Type of organisations</i>	Company, Private non-profit research association, NGO, SME	Association, SME

Source: elaborated by the authors

As is shown in Table 7, the differences between the value chains goes beyond their nature themselves (agrifood vs. plastic). The obtained samples are very different and the type of entities too; making any comparison between them impossible. Thus, the aim of this section is to clearly set out the main SO-LCA results of the two value chains individually, comparing the results, where possible, according to regional or national standards, but never between value chains or organisations themselves.

10.1.1 Methodological notes

- The organisations were asked to provide data from their respective last accounting years. This means that the year of reference of their data differs in some cases between institutions. However, all the data belong to the period 2021-2022.
- In general terms, information has been processed on an aggregated basis per value chain. Individual results are shown only when the data reflects something different from the rest of the organisations in the chain.
- The “Agrifood value chain: average of the organisations average wage per month (W4) (2021-2022)” has been calculated on the salary from 5 organisations since one entity has not included the average salary.
- The Lost time injury frequency rate (W8) has been calculated in a different way adapting it to the number of workers in the analysed organisations (10x⁵ was used instead of 10x⁶ in the formula)

10.1.2 Stakeholder category: workers

Table 8. Workers stakeholder category: results & references

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments	
Forced labour	NEGATIVE	Employment terms	93%	67%	Not applicable		Most of the workers are satisfied with the employment terms	
	NEGATIVE	Forced Labour	0%	0%	Victims rescued from exploitative labour situations in Spain: 514 ⁴	2021	Absence of forced labour	
Fair salary	POSITIVE	Organisation average wage, per month	1.849,90€	1.952,70€	Average wage Murcia Region		Average wage near the regional one	
					1.875,20€ ⁵	2021		
Working hours	POSITIVE	Flexibility	(6/6) 40%	(5/6) 33%	Level of satisfaction with flexibility in the region: 6,97 ⁶		In general, workers are satisfied with the flexibility conditions	
					2010			
	POSITIVE	Full-time staff	94%	97%	Full-time staff in the Region 67,49 % [63]	2021	The average of full-time staff is higher than the regional in both cases	
Equal opportunities/discrimination	POSITIVE	Gender equality	34%	7%	Women employment rate in the Region 44,92% 44,48% (INE) ⁷		2022T4 2021T4	The percentage is lower than the regional rate in both cases
					Percentage of companies with registered GEP out of the number of companies that should have one registered at national level: 23,73% ⁸			
	POSITIVE	Equal opportunities policies	67%	50%	2022		The proportion of organisations with GEP in both value chains is bigger than the national one	
Health and Safety	POSITIVE	Occupational safety measures	90%	67%	No comparable data available		In both cases more than the half of the respondents believe that the safety occupational measures are adequate	
	NEGATIVE	Lost time injury frequency rate	1,28	0	Incidence rate in the Region 3.226,9 ⁹	2021	No comparable data available. Just the number of accidents with sick leave per 100.000 workers	

⁴ <https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/eu/detalle/articulo/Policia-Nacional-y-Guardia-Civil-liberaron-en-2021-a-mas-de-mil-victimas-de-trata-y-explotacion-de-seres-humanos-por-motivos-sexuales-o-laborales/>

⁵ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=13930>

⁶ <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU135/sec2.html>

⁷ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=3996>

⁸ <https://www.uso.es/planes-de-igualdad-solo-una-de-cada-cuatro-empresas-lo-tiene-registrado/>

⁹ <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU135/sec15.html>

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments
							affiliated to the Social Security System
	POSITIVE	Presence of sufficient safety measures	100%	100%	National regulation: BOE-A-1995-24292		The presence of sufficient safety measures is mandatory by the Spanish law
Social benefits, legal issues	NEGATIVE	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	0	0	Social security infringement proceedings in the region: labour relations		In both cases, no violations of law were declared
					672 ¹⁰	2021	
Workers' rights	POSITIVE	Trade unions density	4%	0%	Percentage of employees affiliated to trade unions in Spain:		The percentage of affiliated employees is very low
					12,5% ¹¹	2019	
	POSITIVE	Collective Bargaining Agreement	33%	50%	Total number of CBA in the region:		Compared with the region, the number of CBA is sufficient in both cases
70 ¹²	2021						
Sexual harassment	NEGATIVE	Sexual harassment incidents reported	0	0	Actions against sexual harassment at the national level:		No sexual harassments were declared by the organisations
					642 ¹³	2021	

Forced labour

The first impact subcategory results to be studied is “*forced labour*”¹⁴. With this assessment the aim was to check whether the organisations were not using forced labour.

None of the agrifood value chain actors nor the plastic ones, reported to have forced workers on their staff (W1). Linked to this impact subcategory, the organisations’ staff were asked if they agreed freely on the employment terms (WQ1). In the agrifood value chain case, 93% of the workers surveyed reported having voluntarily accepted the employment terms (i.e. wage, working time, holidays, and terms of resignation). In the case of the plastic value chain just the 67% reported to have accepted them voluntarily.

Fair salary

Fair wages are undoubtedly one of the most important criteria for corporate social responsibility because without fair wages, the workers are not capable of providing for their own needs and the ones of their families. For people to live an adequate life, a “*fair salary*” is necessary [47]. To assess this impact subcategory, we asked the living wage per month

¹⁰ https://www.mites.gob.es/itss/web/Que_hacemos/Estadisticas/docs/2021/02_2021.pdf

¹¹ <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=TUD#>

¹² <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/inicio/-/crem/sicrem/PU134/sec3.html>

¹³

https://www.mites.gob.es/itss/ITSS/ITSS_Descargas/Que_hacemos/Memorias/Memoria_ITSS_2021_8.pdf

¹⁴ Forced or compulsory labour is any work or service that is exacted from any person under the menace of any penalty, and for which that person has not offered himself or herself voluntarily.

of the region (W2), the minimum wage per month¹⁵ at country level (W3) and each organisation average wage per month (W4).

Table 9. Living, minimum & average wage

Murcia's region living wage¹⁶ (W2) <i>Source: Ministry of inclusion, social security and migration, Spain</i>	2021	2022	2023
	-	491,963€	565,37€
Spain minimum wage (W3) <i>Source: statista website</i>	2021	2022	2023
	965€	1.000€	1.080€
Agrifood value chain: average of the organisations. Average wage per month (W4) (2021-2022)		1.849,40 €	
Plastic value chain: average of the organisations average wage per month (W4) (2021-2022)		1.952,70€	

As it is shown in Table 9, in both cases the average salaries are above the region living wage and the national minimum wage. However, for the case of the agrifood value chain, the figure is below the regional average wage (1.875,20€)

Working hours

Inside the workers category, it was also verified if the number of hours effectively worked ("working hours") was in accordance with the national standards. It addresses excessive working time that prohibits a sustainable work life balance as well as too little working hours limiting a satisfying professional life. Hence, the indicators chosen within this subcategory are "*Flexibility (WQ2)*" and "*Full time staff (W5)*". According to the workers survey, in the case of the agrifood value chain, 40% of the respondents are very satisfied with the job flexibility; just 2% of the workers reported to be not satisfied with these conditions (see Figure 6). For the case of the plastic value chain, 67% of the respondents are "neutral" and just 33% are "much satisfied" with these conditions.

Figure 6. Agrifood value chain: Workers' satisfaction with employment flexibility

Table 10. Types of contracts in the Region of Murcia

Workers in the Region of Murcia with full-time contracts (2021)	67,49 %
Workers in the Region of Murcia with partial-time contracts (2021)	20,78 %

¹⁵ Is the lowest gross wage a full-time worker can be remunerated in a specific country, defined by national law and legally binding.

¹⁶ Guaranteed income for a single adult living alone.

Source: Murcia Labour Market Report. Data 2021 [63]

The biggest difference between full-time and part-time employment is the number of hours worked per week. Full-time employees work around 30 to 40 hours a week, while part-time employees typically work less than 30 hours a week.

Within the A2C organisations, in the case of the agrifood value chain, 94%¹⁷ of the employees have full-time contracts (W5), whereas in the case of the plastic one, 97% of the employees have this type of contract.

Equal opportunities/ discrimination

The subcategory “equal opportunities/ discrimination” aims to assess equal opportunity management practices and the presence of discrimination in the opportunities offered to the workers by the organisations.

In our case (considering both value chains workforce), the total percentage of women (W6) in the workforce is 26%. Concretely, 34% of the workforce are women in the agrifood value chain and a 7% in the plastic one.

Regarding the presence of equal opportunity policies (W7), in total (considering both value chains) 67% of the organisations have reported to have formal policies on equal opportunities such as a Gender Equality Plan, as shown in Figure 7. Concretely on the agrifood value chain a 67% have reported to have formal policies on equal opportunities, and in the case of the plastic value chain a 50%.

Due to the heterogeneity of the companies integrating both value chains, it must be remarked that not all the companies are forced to have developed a GEP. According to the Spanish law, just those companies with more than 50 workers must have one, in this case just two companies adding both value chains together.

Figure 7. Formal policies on equal labour opportunities: agrifood and plastic value chains

Health and safety

Since 1950, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) have shared a common definition of occupational health. The definition reads: “Occupational health should aim at: the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations; the prevention amongst workers of departures from health caused by their working conditions; the protection of workers in their employment from risks resulting from factors adverse to health; the placing and maintenance of the worker in an occupational environment adapted to his physiological and psychological capabilities; and, to summarize, the adaptation of work to man and of each man to his job.” [47]. All workers have the right to a safe and healthy workplace, with the “health and safety” subcategory the perception by the workers of adequate occupational safety measures (WQ3), the lost time injury frequency rate (W8) and the presence of sufficient safety measures (W9) are assessed for the selected value chains organisations.

¹⁷ For two organisations the data on staff are related to the year 2021 and for the other two to the year 2022

90% of the agrifood value chain workers reported that the safety measures of the organisations are adequate. However, it is important to highlight that the 10% of the workers chose the option “I am not aware of the company safety measures”. In the case of the plastic value chain, the 67% of the workers who answered the questionnaire reported to believe that the safety measures are adequate and 33% were not aware of these measures.

Subsequently, the lost time injury frequency rate (LTIFR) (W8) was calculated. This rate refers to the number of lost time injuries occurring in a workplace per 100.000 hours worked, it gives a picture of how safe a workplace is for its workers.

In the case of the plastic value chain no work accidents were declared. In the case of the agrifood one, 50% of the organisations reported injured persons (work-related incident) between 2021 & 2022. Concretely, the LTIFR obtained are: 2,34, 10,9 & 1,68. This means, in the first case that 2,34 lost time injuries occur on a jobsite every 100.000 hours worked; in the second case that 10,9 lost time injuries occur on a jobsite every 1 hundred thousand hours worked and in the third one, 1,68 lost time injuries occur on a jobsite every 1 hundred thousand hours worked. It must be taken into account that these figures are not comparable, since the number of workers & hours worked differs between organisations. Taking the weighted average per the workforce, the total LTIFR is 1,28.

On the other hand, the project managers were asked whether the organisations complied with the safety measures obligations required according to their applicable law (W9). In both value chains, all the organisations declared to comply with the mandatory safety measures.

Social benefits, legal issues

Violations of employment regulations, by the employer, are one threat to employees' wellbeing and therefore have a potential social impact. With the “social benefits, legal issues” subcategory, we evaluated if the organisations comply with the current regulations in terms of employment. All the value chain organisations (agrifood & plastic) reported to not having been sanctioned (W10.1-W10.2) during their respective last accounting years due to non-compliance with the current legislation.

Workers' rights

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Art. 20 (UN 1948) every individual has the right to peacefully assembly and to form and join organisations of their choice without being compelled to belong to any association [64]. All workers and employers have the right to establish and to join organisations of their choice, without prior authorization, to promote and defend their respective interests, and to negotiate collectively with other parties. Hence, the “worker's rights” subcategory is measured by the indicator collective agreement (W11.1, W11.2, W11.3, W11.4) which is made up of several measurements (see Social Indicators Battery) and by the indicator trade unions density (WQ4).

Reviewing the information of the agrifood value chain, on the one hand, 33% of the organisations declared to have a collective agreement signed. All of them also stated to have all the related documents available for workers. On the other hand, the 50% of the companies affirmed to have labour organisations (trade union delegates), of which 100% stated that their presence was adequately supported. Moreover, the 83% recognised that employee/union representatives are invited to contribute to planning of large changes in the company (such as launching a new department for example), which affect the working conditions. As for the workers' access to neutral, binding, and independent dispute resolution procedure, just 67% of the organisations declared to have one.

As for the trade unions density, just 4% of the workers reported to be part of an association like that.

Concerning the plastic value chain data, just 1 organisation declared to have a collective agreement signed. This organisation also stated that all the related documents are fully available for employees. Moreover, none of the organisations reported to have trade union delegates and just 50% of the organisations invited, during their last accounting year, employees to contribute to planning of organisation changes. As for the workers access to neutral, binding, and independent dispute resolution procedure, just the 50% of the organisations declared to have one. With reference to the trade unions density, none of the workers who responded to the survey are part of one.

Sexual harassment

According to the ILO sexual-harassment is a sex-based behavior that is unwelcomed and offensive to its recipient. A world of work, free of sexual harassment has become an explicit goal for the member states of the ILO. Within our study, the impact subcategory “*sexual harassment*” was measured with the indicator *sexual harassment incidents reported (W12)* as a means of verification of whether the company registers or not the number of this type of incidents. No such incidents were reported by either organisation in any value chain.

10.1.3 Stakeholder category: value chain actors

Table 11. Value chain actors stakeholder category: results & references

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments
Fair competition	NEGATIVE	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	0	0	Cases opened by the National Commission for the Markets and Competition at national level:		No sanctions were imposed in neither of the value chain organisations
					62 ¹⁸	2021	
Promoting social responsibility	POSITIVE	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	50%	50%	Companies with Corporate Social Responsibility agreements/guides in the Region:		The number of organisations with CSR agreements is low, in both cases, compared with the regional numbers (<i>sample of 128 companies</i>)
					71,9% ¹⁹	2021	
	POSITIVE	Suppliers audit	7%	0%	Percentage of companies that carry out own audits at suppliers on labour rights, forced labour, child labour at national labour		The percentage of organisations that audit their suppliers is very low compared with the national standards

¹⁸ https://www.cnmc.es/sites/default/files/editor_contenidos/CNMC/Memorias/Memoria%202021.pdf

¹⁹

[file:///C:/Users/Usuario/Downloads/Bar%C3%B3metro%20de%20la%20RSC%20en%20Pymes%20de%20la%20Regi%C3%B3n%20de%20Murcia%20\(enero%202022\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Usuario/Downloads/Bar%C3%B3metro%20de%20la%20RSC%20en%20Pymes%20de%20la%20Regi%C3%B3n%20de%20Murcia%20(enero%202022).pdf) (study with a sample of 128 Murcian companies)

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments
					37% ²⁰	2021	
Supplier relationships	POSITIVE	Suppliers' communication relationship	(5/6) 83%	(6/6) 50%	No data available		The supplier's communication relationship has been rated high in both cases
Respect of intellectual property rights	POSITIVE	Use of local intellectual property (nº of conflicts)	0	0	No data available		No sanctions have been reported
Wealth distribution	POSITIVE	Fair price definition	67%	50%	No data available		More than half of the companies have a policy for the definition of a fair price.

Fair competition

Fair competition is the basis of a sound economy since it stimulates efficiency, reduces the costs of products and services, promotes innovation and ensures all organisations have equal opportunities [47]. With the subcategory "*fair competition*" it was intended to analyse the extent to which the organisations' competitive activities are conducted in a fair way and in compliance with legislations. None of the organisations (taking into account both value chains) reported to have been sanctioned in their last accounting year (VC1).

Promoting social responsibility

Globalization has impacted global sourcing and manufacturing thus, enterprises' efforts to promote and monitor social responsibility have become more important, valuable and complex. The "*Promotion of social responsibility*" subcategory seeks to assess whether the value chain organisations promote social responsibility among their suppliers and through its own actions. To this aim and using it as a proxy, we asked the organisations whether they have or not a Corporate Social Responsibility agreement in force (VC2).

In the agrifood value chain, 50% of organisations stated that they have it. On the side of the suppliers, it was assessed the proportion of hired suppliers audited (VC3), being this proportion just a 7% of the total of hired suppliers.

In the plastic value chain, also 50% of the organisations stated to have a Corporate Social Responsibility agreement and none of the hired suppliers were audited.

Supplier relationships

In order to assess the organisations' relationship with their suppliers, they were asked to rate on a scale of 1 (coercive communication) to 6 (very fluent communication) their communication with this group of actors (VC4). In the agrifood value chain, the 85% of the organisations rated this relationship with a 5 and the 17% with a 4. Regarding the plastic value chain, the 50% rated the relationship with a 5 and the 50% with a 6.

Respect of intellectual property rights

Infringements of intellectual property rights are illegal practices and hamper sustainable development [47]. Within the impact subcategory "*respect of intellectual property rights*" the

²⁰ <file:///C:/Users/Usuario/Downloads/deloitte-es-informe-about-9-informe-impacto-social-empresas.pdf>

organisations were asked to report the number of conflicts that arose due to the use of local intellectual property (VC5). The reported conflicts have been 0 (both value chains) during each organisation’s last accounting years.

Wealth distribution

Wealth distribution focuses on how the value is distributed among all the actors of the value chain. An equal distribution is obtained when a fair selling price for a product or service is established. To assess this impact subcategory the organisations were asked whether they have defined a specific policy for deciding a fair price (VC6). In the agrifood value chain, the 67% of the organisations reported to have a specific policy for deciding a fair price, whereas the 17% does not have any specific policy (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Agrifood value chain: Fair price definition: specific policy for deciding a fair price

Figure 9. Plastic value chain: Fair price definition: specific policy for deciding a fair price

As for the plastic one, the 50% reported to have a specific policy for fair price definition and the other 50% no (Figure 9).

10.1.4 Stakeholder category: society

Table 12. Society stakeholder category: results & references

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments
Public commitment to sustainability issues	POSITIVE	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	50%	50%	Percentage of entities that have set public, measurable, and time-bound targets in one of the 17 SDGs in Spain:		Good commitment from organisations in both value chains
					20,68% ²¹	2020	
Contribution to economic development	POSITIVE	Total taxation per capita	16.005,97€	3.722,22€	Tax collection in the Region of Murcia by budget chapters and taxes (Total chapters I, II, III). Amount in millions of euros		No comparable data available.
					338,6 ²²	2021	
Technology development	POSITIVE	Technology transfer program	33%	100%	No data available		The presence of this type of program depends on the organisation main activity
	POSITIVE	Investments in technology development/ transfer	23%	19%	% of enterprises, out of total enterprises, with innovation expenditure in 2020, in the region of Murcia: 12,22% ²³		The ratio of the investments in technology is high compared with the regional one in 2020
Corruption	POSITIVE	Corruption	67%	50%	% of companies with a code of conduct (<i>sample of 128 companies in the region of Murcia</i>)		The development of anticorruption plans is not mandatory by the national law. In both cases the percentage is good
					84% ²⁴	2021	
Poverty alleviation	POSITIVE	Poverty alleviation program	33%	0%	No data available		The number of initiatives/ plans/ activities to fight against poverty is very low

²¹ <https://www.mdsocialesa2030.gob.es/agenda2030/documentos/contribucion-empresarial-eds.pdf>

²² <https://www.hacienda.gob.es/Documentacion/Publico/Tributos/Estadisticas/Recaudacion/2020/Analisis-estadistico-recaudacion-2020.pdf>

²³ <https://www.ine.es/jaxi/Datos.htm?path=/t14/p061/a2020/i0/&file=07001.px>

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Public commitment to sustainability issues

A broader interpretation of social responsibility implies that organisations not only consider sustainable issues at the organisation level but also in relation to their community and society [47]. Thus, public commitment is a very relevant indicator to analyse the organisation's understanding of social responsibility. To measure this public commitment, the organisations were asked whether they had any agreements in place on sustainability issues (S1). In total, considering both value chains, just a 50% of the organisations reported to have an agreement of this nature.

Contribution to economic development

Economic development is a basic requirement in the struggle against poverty and hunger and organisations play an important role in creating sufficient wealth to satisfy basic material needs. To evaluate the impact subcategory "contribution to economic development" the indicator "*total taxation per capita*" (S2) has been used. Taxes can be used as a proxy of organisations contribution to the society's well-being. To calculate this indicator, all the companies were asked to provide the total taxes paid in their respective last accounting years, by all typologies (personal related, excluding capital). Then, the total figure of paid taxes has been divided by the total number of workforce forming the analysed value chain. The taxation per capita in the agrifood value chain amounts to 16.005,97€ and to 3.722,22€ in the plastic one.

Technology development

In order to promote sustainability and circular economy technology development is key. Modern technologies potential is twofold: it may reduce environmental impacts and help to overcome under-development. The "technology development" impact subcategory has been evaluated by the indicators "*technology transfer program*" (S3) & "*Investments in technology development/transfer*" (S4).

Technology transfer is a structural process of learning, which requires several inputs such as coordination between technology developers and users. It is a social concern that organisations contribute to technology development, by engaging in partnerships with other organisations in joint research and development programs or private-public partnerships. In the agrifood value chain, just 33% of the organisations have declared to have a technology transfer program in place in their respective last accounting years, whereas in the plastic one the 100% have a plan of this kind. As for the rate of investments in technology transfer, just 23% of the agrifood organisations investments were dedicated to this type of activities. The rate in the case of the plastic value chain is lower, being the ratio of investment a 19%. This indicator is a proxy for the effort made by the organisation in development and/or technology transfer, as well as the degree of technological innovation that a product incorporates.

Corruption

Corruption takes money out of the official system and thus has an impact on the state income. This subcategory assesses whether an organisation has implemented appropriate measures to prevent corruption. In this study, the measure considered has been to have a formalized commitment to prevent corruption (S5). 67% of the agrifood value chain organisations stated to have developed official actions to avoid corruption and in the case of the plastic one just a 50%.

Poverty alleviation

Poverty reduction and economic stability are crucial drivers to protect the environment and the local communities, thus with the “*poverty alleviation*” subcategory it was aimed to assess the presence or not (S6) of proactive activities, such as strategies, action plans, investment, to reduce the poverty of the society. The majority of the agrifood value chain organisations (concretely the 67%) reported to no have developed any poverty alleviation program. In the case of plastic organisations none of them have a program of this kind.

10.1.5 Stakeholder category: local community

Table 13. Local community stakeholder category: results & references

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments	
Access to material resources	POSITIVE	Environmental management system	50%	50%	Number of organisations with Community Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) in Spain	973 ²⁵	2021	The percentage might be adequate taking into account the organisations heterogeneity
Access to immaterial resources	POSITIVE	Community education initiatives	67%	50%	No data available		Both percentages are equal or higher than 50%	
Delocalization and migration	POSITIVE	Immigrant workforce rate	6%	15%	Employment rate foreign nationality in the Region:		In both cases the percentage is lower than the region	
					55,51 ²⁶ 58,77	2021T4 2022T4		
Delocalization and migration	POSITIVE	Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	0	50%	No data available		Few organisational processes for migrant integration	
Cultural heritage	POSITIVE	Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage	67%	50%	Community CSR practices: support and financial resources for cultural or sports activities in the community in the region of Murcia		Compared with the data from the region (<i>sample of 128 companies</i>), the percentages lower	
					76% ²⁷	2021		
Safe and healthy living conditions	POSITIVE	Promotion of community health	33%	50%	No data available		The dedication of financial resources to strengthen community health is scarce	
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	(5/6) 67%	(6/6) 50%	No data available		The organisations rate in both cases their diversity of stakeholders as diverse or very diverse	
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Number of meetings with community stakeholders	53	58	No data available		In both cases there were meetings held by organisations	

²⁵ <https://www.ine.es/dyngs/ODS/es/indicador.htm?id=5117>

²⁶ <https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=4227#!tabs-tabla>

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[file:///C:/Users/Usuario/Downloads/Bar%C3%B3metro%20de%20la%20RSC%20en%20Pymes%20de%20la%20Regi%C3%B3n%20de%20Murcia%20\(enero%202022\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Usuario/Downloads/Bar%C3%B3metro%20de%20la%20RSC%20en%20Pymes%20de%20la%20Regi%C3%B3n%20de%20Murcia%20(enero%202022).pdf) (study with a sample of 128 Murcian companies)

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference	Comments
	POSITIVE	Organisational support (volunteer-hours or financial) for community initiatives	Hours: 800 Financial resources: 424.325,80€	Hours: 0 Financial resources: 20.858,80€	No data available		In both cases more financial resources than volunteer hours have been dedicated
Local employment	POSITIVE	Workforce hired locally	15,3%	15,5%	No data available		The percentage of locally hired workers is low in both cases
	POSITIVE	Spending on locally based suppliers	36,9%	57,1%	CSR Practices with Suppliers: Always try to buy from local suppliers (Murcia region). 80% ²⁸	2021	According to the data obtained from the <i>sample of 128 companies</i> , on average the organisations of both two-value chain spend less in local suppliers
Secure living conditions	NEGATIVE	Security complaints by the community	0	0	No data available		No complaints were declared by any of the organisations

Access to material resources

Organisations may contribute to sustainable development by protecting existing natural resources and their related ecosystem services. With the impact subcategory “Access to material resources” the aim was to assess whether the organisations have a certified environmental management system (LC1). The idea is to take the existence of certified EMS as a proxy for the commitment of companies in a sector to environmental protection.

In both cases, the 50% of the organisations declared to have an EMS in force in its last accounting year.

Access to immaterial resources

Within the “access to immaterial resources” impact subcategory, it was wanted to assess whether the organisations may build community relations and improve access to immaterial resources by promoting education in the community (LC2). The reason for this indicator relies on the fact that organisations should also transfer knowledge to the community through formal training programs and general community education initiatives [47].

The 67% of the agrifood value chain have declared to develop in their respective last accounting year, initiatives targeted to foster education in the community. As for the plastic value chain, the 50% reported to have initiatives to foster the education in the community.

Delocalization and migration

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Due to its geographical location and its productive system, the Region of Murcia is one of the regions that receives the higher number of immigrants. In the case of migrant workers entering a community, the organisation should consider how well workers will integrate with more permanent residents. Organisations should provide opportunities for communication and education between migrant workers and permanent residents to minimise risks [47]. To assess it, first the indicator “*Immigrant workforce rate*” (LC3) was defined, together with an indicator to assess if the companies have any internal procedure for integrating migrant workers in the community (LC4).

The ratio of immigrant employees in the workforce on average for the agrifood value chain is 6% and in the plastic value chain is 15%. None of the organisations in the agrifood chain declared to have any internal procedures to integrate migrant workers into the community, whereas in the plastic value chain, one organisation declared to have these types of policies.

Cultural heritage

As a proxy to assess if the organisations promote and preserve cultural heritage, they were asked if in their respective last accounting years, have dedicated financial resources to support and promote cultural heritage (i.e., cultural activities and events) (LC5). The 67% of the agrifood organisations reported “Yes”, and the 50% of the plastic value chain organisations also reported “Yes” in this question.

Safe and healthy living conditions

Organisations may influence and contribute to the health of local communities. Moreover, communication is key, concretely when their activities can generate potential impacts of their operations to surrounding communities.

The indicator established for this impact subcategory has been “*Promotion of community health*” (LC6); the organisations were asked if they dedicated, in their respective last accounting year, financial resources to strengthen community health (i.e., through shared community access to organisation health resources). The 33% of the agrifood value chain & the 50% of the plastic value chain organisations declared that they had dedicated financial resources to community health promotion.

Community engagement

An organisation should attempt to engage with a broad range of stakeholders that represent balanced community interests (“*Community engagement*” impact subcategory). To capture the diversity of engaged stakeholders, the organisations were asked to indicate, using a Likert scale, how diverse their engaged stakeholders are, being 1 “not very diverse” and 6 “very diverse” (LC7). As shown in Figure 10 the majority of the agrifood value chain organisations consider the diversity of their engaged stakeholders on a level of 5 (67%). In the plastic value chain, the diversity of engaged stakeholders is divided into 4 (50%) and 6 (50%)

Moreover, the number of meetings held with community stakeholders (LC8) was also asked in order to understand if the relationship of the organisation with its community stakeholders is recurrent. A total of 53 meetings were held between

Figure 10. Agrifood value chain: Diversity of stakeholder groups engaged with the organization

2021-2022 on the side of the agrifood chain and 58 meetings were held among the organisations of the plastic value chain.

Organisations can also foster community engagement through direct involvement in community initiatives and/ or through financial support to this type of projects. With the indicator “*Organisations support for local initiatives*” (LC9) it was wanted to know if the organisations support or not, and how, the community initiatives that might be carried out in their respective communities. In the agrifood value chain, a total of 800 volunteer-hours of organisational support and a total of 424.325,80€ of financial resources have been dedicated to this type of initiatives. In the case of the plastic chain, no volunteer-hours were dedicated and a total of 20.858,80€ of financial resources were dedicated to support community initiatives.

Local employment

Organisations have great potential to encourage sustainable development through local hiring preferences. Local employees have unique knowledge of important community issues and can help the organisation build strong community relations. Furthermore, local employment improves the living conditions of communities, limits the risk of poverty and keeps people from emigrating. In addition, the cooperation with local suppliers further strengthens local economies [64].

Thus, this subcategory assesses the role of an organisation in directly or indirectly affecting local employment using as indicators the “*workforce hired locally*” (LC10) & “*the spending on locally based suppliers*” (LC11).

The ratio of local hired workers is 15,3%, in the agrifood and 15,5% in the plastic chain, whereas the ratio of expenditure on locally based suppliers is 36,9% in the first one and 57,1% in the second analysed value chain.

Secure living conditions

Organisations having an impact on local communities is a fact. With this subcategory the objective was to assess if the local community has complained regarding the organisation practices of private personnel security, through the indicator “*security complaints by the community*” (LC12). The number of reported complaints in total (considering all the organisations) is 0.

10.1.6 Stakeholder category: consumers

Table 14. Consumers stakeholder category: results & references

Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference
Health and Safety	POSITIVE	Labelling	83%	50%	No data available	In some cases, this indicator is not applicable.
	NEGATIVE	Consumer complaints	92	3	No data available	Information not publicly available for the region.
	POSITIVE	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	83%	50%	Number of ISO 9001 certificates in Spain 31.318 ²⁹ 2021	In some cases, this indicator is not applicable. The majority of the organisations have a system of this type
Feedback mechanism	POSITIVE	Presence of consumers feedback mechanism	67%	0%	% of companies that conduct customer satisfaction surveys in the region (sample of 128 companies)	Lower in agrifood value chain, inexistent in the plastic one
					76% ³⁰ 2021	
Consumer privacy	NEGATIVE	Consumers complaints related to breach of privacy	0	0	% companies respecting customer data privacy in the region of Murcia (sample of 128 companies)	No complaints were registered
					90% ³¹ 2021	
Transparency	POSITIVE	Organisation communication transparency	6/6	5/6	% of companies in the region of Murcia that communicate information to their customers with full transparency (sample of 128 companies)	All the organisations rated their communication transparency as high
					86% ³² 2021	

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<https://www.iso.org/committee/54998.html?t=KomURwikWDLiuB1P1c7SjLMLEAgXOA7emZHKGWyn8f3KQUTU3m287NxnPA3Dluxm&view=documents#section-isodocuments-top>

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Impact subcategory	Social influence	Indicators	Value (Agrifood)	Value (Plastic)	Reference	Year of data reference
End-of-life responsibility	POSITIVE	Internal management systems	33%	50%	No data available	In some cases this indicator is not applicable.

Health and Safety

Consumer health and safety refers to the consumers’ rights to be protected against products and services that may be hazardous to health or life (ISO 26000, 2008). To assess this protection three indicators were defined: products informative labels (C1), number of consumer complains referring to the quality of the commercialised products/ services (C2) & Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc (C3).

The data for the agrifood value chain shows that the 83% of the organisations affirmed to have informative labelling, where the main product features are explained. The rest of the organisations (17%) indicated that this measure did not apply to them. As for the consumer complaints, a total of 92 complaints have been declared. Moreover, 82% declared to have a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System.

If we check the information provided by the plastic value chain organisations, 50% affirmed to have informative labelling, a total of 3 complaints were registered and the 50% of the organisations does have a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System.

Feedback mechanism

The right to be heard, regarding product and service complaints through communication mechanisms, should be included in management measures regarding consumer satisfaction (C4). 67% of the organisations reported having a mechanism for consumers to provide feedback and 17% stated that this questions was not applicable. On the plastic value chain side, none of the organisations reported to have any consumers feedback mechanism (Figure 11)

Figure 11. Agrifood value chain: Consumers feedback mechanism

Consumer privacy

Consumer privacy concerns include protecting the confidentiality of consumer data, limiting personal information gathered, restricting use of data to its original or agreed-upon purpose, and protecting data from external theft and/or misuse [47]. This subcategory examines whether organisational management systems work to respect and protect consumer privacy. In cases where organisations share personal information, procedures should exist for individuals to dispute, remove, or correct inaccurate information (C5). No complaints related to breach of privacy or loss of data by consumers were reported in either value chains.

Transparency

Figure 12 Agrifood value chain: Organisations communication transparency

Organisations were asked to rate (using a Likert scale) their effort on communicating all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way towards consumers (C6). Organisational transparency is important since it enables an informed choice for the consumer without intent to mislead.

Being 1 equivalent to “Not very transparent communication” and 6 to “Very transparent communication”, the majority (50%) of the agrifood organisations rated their communication as “Very transparent”. The plastic organisations are more divided, rating the 50% their communication with a 5 and the other 50% with a 6 (Figure 12).

End-of-life responsibility

In this impact subcategory the defined was “*Internal management systems*” (C7). This indicator is intended to know if the organisations have internal management systems that ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options for products. In a product life cycle, end-of-life refers to product disposal, reuse, or recycling. In an environmental context, this concept is commonly referred to as extended producer responsibility. Product disposal can lead to significant environmental and social concerns. Regarding the agrifood value chain, 2 organisations have reported to have a management system of this kind, 3 have reported that this was not applicable to their type of business and 1 have not provided information. As for the plastic one, just one organisation has reported to have this type of system and for one this question was not applicable.

10.2 Limitations

Although many researchers have pointed out that sustainability is a multidimensional concept (environmental, economic & social aspects), the growing sensitivity on climate change and environmental issues has focused on the most recent discussion of scholars, political leaders and public opinion on environmental sustainability while neglecting social sustainability [65]. From a managerial perspective, social sustainability is essential, because by affecting the organisational model, it impacts the company's performance and also can impinge upon the trust of internal and external stakeholders.

Regardless of the growing interest in the CE, the social dimension of circularity practices is still unexplored also due to the absence of appropriate comparable metrics to assess social impacts. Therefore, another barrier for implementing social sustainability in circular economy related firms is the lack of social performance measurement tools comparable to those already used to assess technological and operational performance. Existing tools are limited in their effectiveness by the lack of quantitative data linking social impacts to company operations. As a result, although many methods of assessing social sustainability have been proposed, the quantitative aspects of the social performance of agrifood enterprises have not yet been sufficiently clarified, especially regarding the relationships between social impacts and corresponding technological performance, as well as the supply chain.

Furthermore, there are several methodological limitations that should be considered when talking about the S-LCA & SO-LCA:

The SO-LCA methodology is very recent, with less than 3 years since published.

In 2009 UNEP launched the first Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). Since then, researchers and practitioners have used these Guidelines to assess the positive and negative social and socio-economic impacts of products over their lifecycle. However, according to the Imperial Life Cycle Network [66], since 2009 just between 1.000 to 5.000 studies on S-LCA were published. Particularly, the SO-LCA was included in the 2020 edition, not in the 2009, thus this methodological variant is even more incipient and there are less references.

Circular economy has very scarce examples of S-LCA studies.

This fact makes potential comparability exercises more difficult, limiting the scope of the results [33].

Lack of generic databases for background processes & absence of benchmarking possibility.

As SO-LCA is a young concept, performance tracking may be even more difficult, also considering the challenges in the collection of social data. Moreover, the results are not intended to be used in comparative assertions disclosed to the public. Due to the lack of consistent basis for comparison between organisation, as different organisations have a vastly variable product portfolio, the comparability step is neither meaningful nor robust [31].

The S-LCA methodology does not connect the circular economy activities with the social indicators.

This approach does not link specific activities with the respective social impact pathways. There is no attributable cause-effect chain for social life cycle inventory results to impact. While in the environmental evaluation (ELCA), the externalities are going to be assessed to benchmark the environmental benefits of the new circular approach and compare it with the current linear approach, in the social approach this correlation cannot be evaluated. Thus,

in the case of Agro2Circular, the potential changes generated in social terms in the organisations involved cannot be attributed to the technological change generated as a result of the project.

10.3 Workers' awareness results

The workers' questionnaire was sent to the following organisations within the different value chains (agrifood & plastic): PROEXPORT, GWC, CETEC, CITROMIL, CTNC, PRIMAFRIO, MCTS, LOLOBIO, ALMOND, DMC, IRIS. The aim was to gather as much data as possible to analyse at this first screening step the awareness and consciousness regarding circular economy of the employees working in the different organisations where A2C is being deployed. At the end of the project, we will be able to compare the evolution of workers' attitudes towards the different survey items.

The results by topic are shown below.

10.3.1 Sample characterization

The **total number of answers** has been **115**. If we divide the number of responses between the value chains, 21% of the responses are in the plastic chain and 79% in the agrifood chain.

As for the sample gender, the 46% of the respondents were male, the 53% female and 1% preferred not to answer. Regarding the age of the respondents, the big majority (47%) are between 35-50 years old, then the 31% are between 16 and 35 years old and just 21% are over 50 (1% didn't answer the question).

In terms of job positions, the majority of the respondents are technicians, followed by researchers/ consultants, project managers and administrative workers.

The sample educational level is in general high. Only 4% of the employees who responded to the survey have high school education and 19% vocational training; 43% have a degree, Bachelor's degree or Diploma and the 34% of the respondents have a Master's degree or PhD.

Finally the employees were also asked for their type of contract. 94% of the respondents have a permanent contract, whereas the 13% have a temporary contract. 5% of the respondents have an internship contract.

10.3.2 NEP

In order to evaluate the environmental concern, the revised NEP scale is used [41], [67]. The structure of the NEP consists of five conceptual interrelated facets underlying a general ecological worldview, expressed through fifteen statements or items. Items are designed to tap each of the five hypothesized facets of an ecological worldview: the reality of **limits to growth** (1, 6, 11), **antianthropocentrism** (2, 7, 12), the **fragility of nature's balance** (3, 8, 13), **rejection of exemptionalism** (4, 9, 14) and the **possibility of an ecocrisis** (5, 10, 15). Respondents are asked to indicate the strength of their agreement or disagreement with each statement, using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. Responses to these fifteen statements are then used to evaluate the different dimensions proposed by the authors as part of the environmental awareness construct [49]. Although the dimensionality of the NEP has been questioned, we will use the scales proposed by the authors for descriptive

purposes, in order to better explore the different nuances of the environmental awareness construct in our sample [41]. Respondents are asked to indicate the strength of their agreement or disagreement with each statement. Responses to these fifteen statements are then used to construct various statistical measures of environmental concerns. The eight odd-numbered items are worded so that agreement indicates a proecological view, and the seven even numbered ones so that disagreement indicates a proecological worldview. After correcting the directionality of the items, the geometric mean and standard deviation of the results obtained in the NEP for each dimension or scale were calculated.

In Figure 13 the mean of *limits to growth* scale is shown. Within these items, the following statements are included: “We are approaching the limit of the number of people the earth can support”, “The earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them” & “The earth is like a spaceship with very limited room and resources”. The aggregated mean is 2,95 (SD: 0,91). As for the scale *anti-anthropocentrism* (Figure 14), the following statements are included: “Humans have the right to modify the natural environment to suit their needs”, “Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist” & “Humans were meant to rule over the rest of nature”. The total average of this item is 3,36 (SD: 0,63). Regarding *fragility of nature’s balance* (Figure 15), the following items are included: “When humans interfere with nature it often produces disastrous consequences”, “The balance of nature is strong enough to cope with impacts of modern industrial nations” & “The balance of nature is very delicate and easily upset”. The mean is 3,84 (SD: 0,71). The fourth scale is *rejection of exemptionalism* (Figure 16), and is composed of the following statements: “Human ingenuity will insure that we do NOT make the earth unlivable”, “Despite our special abilities humans are still subject to the laws of nature” & “Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it”. The total mean of the item is 3,31 (SD: 0,71). The last scale is *possibility of an ecocrisis* (Figure 17), which is composed of the following items: “Humans are severely abusing the environment”, “The so-called „ecological crisis” facing humankind has been greatly exaggerated” & “If things continue on their present course, we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe”. The mean of this scale in the sample is 3,79 (SD: 0,80).

Figure 13. NEP: Limits to growth (1,6,11)

Figure 14. NEP: Antianthropocentrism (2,7,12)

Figure 15. NEP: Fragility of nature's balance (3, 8, 13)

Figure 16. NEP: Rejection of exemptionalism (4, 9, 14)

Figure 17. NEP; Possibility of an ecocrisis (5, 10, 15)

10.3.3 Survey con consumers: awareness

To the question "Where would you say the majority of peoples' knowledge of what can and can't be recycled comes from?", the most voted options were: media (18%) and social networks and internet (17%). In "Other entries" (25%) are included: family, friends, neighbors, local waste management company and consumers' & environmental associations (Figure 18).

Figure 18 Q11: Where would you say the majority of peoples’ knowledge of what can and can’t be recycled comes from?

Moreover, the 68% of the respondents are “strongly agree” with the fact that people need to know where the items go after its collection.

The employees were also asked why they think it is important to correctly separate (Figure 19). The most selected option has been “To reduce environmental pollution” (37%), followed by “For ethical choices and future generation” (27%). The less preferred option has been “For economic benefits” (9%).

Figure 19 Q13: Why do you think it is important to correctly separate waste?

10.3.4 Survey on consumers: desire

This section was aimed to know which option is the most valued by the employees to solve the problem of plastic recycling and also to find out, according to the employees’ view, what can authorities do to make recycling easier.

Figure 20. Q14: How could the problem of plastic recycling be reduced?

As it can be seen in Figure 20, the most valued options to reduce the problem of plastic recycling are to support the use of alternative materials on an informative, cultural and economic level & to inform consumers and firms on existing alternatives. The option with the highest proportion of “strongly disagree” is to drastically limit their areas of use by law. In terms of possible action by the authorities, the most highly rated by the employees have been “Incentivizing separate collection with payments/discounts on the bill” (59% | fully agree) & “Make the recycling bins more visible by using signs” (46% | fully agree). “Fine those who neglect” & “Suggestions to reduce the amount of personal waste” were the two worst rated options.

Figure 21. Q15: Is there anything that you feel authorities can do to make recycling easier?

10.3.5 Circular economy: awareness

In this section employees were asked about their habits as consumers in order to analyse their attitudes and awareness towards **circular economy**.

Figure 22. Q16.1 I separate the household waste according to type (compost, plastic, paper, glass)

To the statement “I separate the household waste according to type”, the 51% of the respondents answered that they “fully agree”. The 33% “agree” and the 9% are “neutral”. The main reasons chosen by the respondents who answered “disagree” & “strongly disagree” for not separating the household waste are:

- I don't have space to separate it (30%)
- The places where I can take it are far away (22%)
- I give away the clothes and appliances (11%)
- Others (11%)
- There are no recycling bins or facilities in my area (8%)
- Other responses (19%): It's too complicated, I don't have time, I don't believe it has a relevant impact, I don't have waste / I reuse it, I don't know how or where to recycle it & it's not my responsibility.

In Figure 23 different employees' attitudes are shown towards their behaviour when they are on holidays, regarding the use of green points and their recycling approaches. Regarding the first item, the 37% of the respondents strongly disagree with the idea of changing their behaviour when they are on holiday. Just 5% fully agree with the statement. Therefore, the majority of the respondents (53%) fully agreed with the use of green points for the disposal of appliances or electronic devices, cooking oil and other types of waste. Lastly, it is necessary to highlight that the 56% completely disagreed with the statement “I don't usually recycle because I don't know how to do it well”.

Figure 23 Q16.2, Q16.3, Q16.4 responses

Figure 24 Q16.5 Before buying a new product, I look for the possibility to buy it second hand

The employees' attitudes towards second hand purchasing (Figure 24) were also analysed. Just 8% of the respondents fully agree with the behaviour of searching for the possibility of a second hand product before buying a new one and a 13% agreed. The 30% of the respondents were neutral towards the statement.

Most frequently purchased second hand products are:

- Books (23%)
- Furniture (18%)
- Consumer electronics (smartphone, tablet, smart band...) (15%)
- Clothing (10%)
- Household appliances (washing machine, dishwasher, refrigerator...) (8%)
- Other responses (25%): Household electronics (TV, sound system, computer...), small appliances (iron, blender, toaster...), others, shoes & children's clothing

Apart from buying second hand products, the respondents were also asked whether they usually repair products in order to extend their life span (see Figure 25). The majority of the respondents do send their products to repair. The most frequently repaired products are:

- Household appliances (washing machine, dishwasher, refrigerator...) (19%)
- Household electronics (TV, sound system, computer...) (17%)
- Furniture (14%)
- Clothing (12%)
- Small appliances (iron, blender, toaster...) (12%)
- Other responses (26%): consumer electronics (smartphone, tablet, smart band...), shoes, children’s clothing & others

Figure 25 Q16.6 I usually send products to repair in order to extend their life span

In Figure 26 several respondents’ attitudes towards circular behaviours are gathered. In the first place, just 16% fully agree with the fact that the public administration restricts or forbids some mobility behaviours, the majority of the respondents are neutral to this statement (26%). Secondly, they were asked whether when choosing a means of transport, they tried to choose the less pollutant. The majority of the respondents are also neutral to this statement (47%). Lastly, employees were also asked if they don’t repair it and buy a new product when something stops working, to which most of the respondents disagreed (30%) or strongly disagreed (30%).

Figure 26 Q16.7, Q16.10, Q16.11 responses

Moreover, the attitude towards the waste of food was also asked. To the statement “Many times, my fruits and vegetables go old and I throw them away”, 7% of the respondents fully agreed, 16% agreed, 17% are neutral, 36% disagreed and 25% fully disagreed. In addition, the 35% of the respondents agree with the statement “I use more and more apps on my smartphone”.

This statement may be related to the relative novelty of the circular economy concept: although it started to appear in several books in 1989, it was not until 2015 that this concept began to gain importance [68]. In this regard, respondents were also asked if they knew the definition of circular economy. The 76% of the respondents affirmed to know the concept and just the 28% did not know it.

Beyond the level of awareness of citizens and their predisposition to buy recycled, remanufactured, repaired or reused products, it is very important to see the perception of quality they have of these products. As we can see in Figure 27, the perception of quality of remanufactured products is better than that of reused. In other words, those that have undergone a greater transformation with respect to the original product and, therefore, those that can offer more guarantees, are the best valued in terms of quality.

Figure 27 Q18 Perception of quality according to type of product

In Figure 28 are represented the most carried-out sustainable practices by the respondents. As we can see, the most performed actions are: switching off the lights at home when they are not being used, taking your own shopping bag when going to the grocery store & replacing light bulbs with LED lights. In “Other entries” the following activities are included:

- I look for cosmetics and personal hygiene products that have not been tested on animals;
- I look for perfumes with bottles that can be reused;
- I buy sustainable clothing;
- I look for cosmetics and personal hygiene products with biodegradable packaging;
- I buy clothes from stores which give coupons for recycling used clothes.

Figure 28 Q19: Most carried-out sustainable actions by citizens

Lastly, respondents were asked about the most relevant factor that would motivate them to shift to a more sustainable behaviour (see below Figure 29). Instead of messages that are sometimes considered diffuse, respondents demand other types of initiatives which motivate them to have more sustainable behaviours:

- Economic incentives from the Public Administration for those companies offering products and services that are more sustainable in order to make easier accessing such products and services;
- Economic incentives from companies or the Public Administration for those people who behave more sustainably;
- More and more information about the choice of products and services that we can buy or use;

In “Other responses”, the following aspects are included:

- Fines on companies offering products and services that are less sustainable imposed by the Public Administration in order to make more difficult accessing such products and services;
- Fines on people who behave less sustainably imposed by the Public Administration;
- Increase of air pollution;
- Other entries

Figure 29 Q20. Most relevant factors which would motivate citizens to shift to a more sustainable behaviour

10.4 Social analysis conclusions

In this section the main conclusions of the previous sections are presented.

In general, organisations from both value chains have a great social performance towards the “workers” stakeholder. If we review per impact subcategory, those employees who responded to the questionnaire are, on average, satisfied with the employment terms. Within employment terms, we have considered wages, working time & holidays. The majority in both cases reported to have accepted these conditions voluntarily. Moreover, no forced labour has been declared. If any of the organisations had declared the existence of forced labour, it would be punishable by law.

As for the salary, in both value chains, the average of the average organisations wage is near or above the average regional one. Wages are undoubtedly one of the most important factors in ensuring the workers' welfare. Moreover, it should not be forgotten that wages are closely linked to the economic cycle and depend, to a large extent, on the sector of activity being analysed. In the latest labour market report for the Murcia region [63], the good performance and positive growth prospects of the entire agri-food and beverage industry are particularly highlighted. This is due to the improvement in the eating habits of the population. As for the plastics-related industry, the forecasts are also positive regarding the maintenance of production. With this forecast, although the average wage is close to the average for the region, there is always room for improvement taking into consideration the good perspectives in the near future of both sectors.

Linked with the workers' welfare is the dedication to work of the employees. The percentage of workers fully satisfied with the flexibility for work-life balance, rest and overtime provided by the organisations is not very high. Although there are workers satisfied in the plastic value chain with the work flexibility, the number of neutral answers is very high, concretely 67%. This is a matter for improvement on the plastic value chain. Related to flexibility and hours dedicated to work is the employee's type of contracts. Schedules for part-time roles tend to be more flexible, often with rotating shifts, whereas full-time positions have more consistent schedules. Full-time employees are typically also eligible for more benefits than part-time employees, being the full-time employment normally more beneficial for workers (even more taking into account the flexibility of the Spanish labour market). The percentage of full-time workers in both value chains are above the regional average. Probably, this is due to the nature of the organisations analysed, based on a more industrial/ services rather than the primary sector, which has always been a sector with a much higher rate of temporary employment due to the nature of the activity itself.

Then, it is true that over the last fourteen years in the Region of Murcia, female employment has declined in comparison to male employment, as in 2007, 61,63% of contracts went to men and 38,37% to women. However, in 2021 both sexes are represented by 66,86 % and 33,14 % respectively. And on balance 2007-2021, the number of contracts for men grew by 38,28 % and for women by 10,10 % [44]. By this what is stated is that there is still a great gender gap in the region of Murcia labour market, which is reflected in the percentage of female recruitment in the analysed organisations in general terms. The ratio of women in the workforce in both value chains is very low compared with the women employment rate in the region. It is true that individually, there are some organisations with a good ratio of female employment, but as we are working with aggregated data by value chain, this point can be improved in both cases. On the other hand, and very positively assessed, the percentage of organisations with a GEP is significantly higher compared to the reference

data, especially, since only two of the organisations, considering both chains, are obliged to have it.

Another component of workers' well-being is health and safety. Workers from both value chains who completed the survey have generally, considered safety measures to be adequate. Moreover, at the organisational level, 100% of the organisations have stated that they comply with the safety measures required by law. The combination of these two factors is probably the reason why the number of reported accidents is so low overall. However, it is necessary to add as a point for improvement that in both value chains there was a percentage of workers who responded that they were not aware of the organisations' security measures. Prevention is very important, and workers must be properly informed. This point needs to be improved in both value chains.

Freedom of association is also an important right to be considered. As shown in the results section, the percentage of workers affiliated to a trade union is in both cases very low. This is a normal trend in the Spanish labour market due, in part, to the change in the nature of work itself (from a permanent job for life to a temporary job). In this indicator, however, there is room for improvement in general. Concretely the number of CBAs, the invitation to workers/ trade unions to the planning tables and the access to neutral conflict resolution processes are points to enhance in both value chains.

In this global world, the chosen value chain actors by organisations matters. In our case study, several categories related to these actors have been evaluated. To sum up, in general the number of CSR agreements can be enhanced, concretely in the plastic value chain should be further promoted, although the numbers reported in the agrifood value chain are not very high either. Having a CSR agreement can bring many intangible benefits to organisations and are a very good starting point for promoting sustainable practices. There is also much room for improvement in the audit of suppliers in both value chains. Furthermore, the existence of mechanisms for the definition of a fair price is evaluated very positively since an equal wealth distribution is obtained when a fair selling price for a product is established.

As for the indicators related to society as stakeholder, the average percentage of entities with a sustainability agreement in both cases exceeds the national benchmark. In total, if we add together the organisations of the two value chains, 50% have an agreement of this type. Although it is true that the national standards are exceeded, there is always room for improvement, concretely in this case of organisations participating in the framework of a project such as A2C. As for the indicator of contribution to economic development, no benchmark data has been found for comparison. In future analyses, it would be interesting to delve deeper into this indicator, as the per capita rate of taxes paid can function as a very accurate proxy. If we talk about technological development, we have to take into account the framework in which the analysis takes place. According to the results of the surveys, it is true that in the agrifood chain the number of technology transfer programs in the organisations should be improved. In addition, it should be noted that, with regard to the ratio of investment in technological development, although the ratio for both value chains is higher than the reference figure, this corresponds to the year 2020. In 2020 the world economy was affected by COVID-19, therefore the data should be analysed taking the above into consideration. Despite the size, 67% of organisations in the agrifood chain and 50% of organisations in the plastics chain have developed an anti-corruption plan. This is very positive as corruption can not only harm the organisations themselves, but society as a whole. Finally, the big point for improvement in this category is the poverty alleviation

programs. It would be advisable for those entities with a CSR agreement to include activities related to this issue in their plan to carry out.

The impact of the organisations' activities in the local community matters. In this case, the funding dedicated to promote cultural heritage and the community education activities are taken into account by the value chain organisations. However, for the agrifood value chain the number of initiatives to promote community health could be improved. Taking into account the heterogeneity of the organisations the performance in general terms is not bad. The low rate of foreign workers in the workforce in both value chains is striking, especially if we take into account that Murcia is a region that receives a lot of foreign workers (in 2021 the rate of hiring foreigners was the highest in Spain [63]). This is probably the reason why organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community are absent. As for the community engagement, in both value chains the stakeholder diversity has been rated as high and the number of meetings with community actors have been similar in both cases. If we analyse the resources dedicated to the community, the number of volunteer hours is very scarce in both cases; this might be improved. In the future, the category of locally recruited workers should be further analysed. Getting micro-level figures for comparison is very difficult as employment figures are usually at the city level. This means that there is no possibility of comparison. Local prosperity depends not only on the direct jobs created, but also on the choice of suppliers (local or international). In our case, the proportion of spending on local suppliers is very low in both value chains. Future studies will analyse the causes of this low ratio.

The presence of consumers feedback mechanisms is very important as well as the presence of protection mechanisms. The results of this section can be improved in general in both value chains. In relation to information labelling, the percentage of organisations claiming to have it is not acceptable. However, the presence of consumer feedback mechanisms is a point for improvement in both value chains. Especially the plastic value chain needs to include consumer feedback mechanisms. On the positive side, transparency in communication towards the consumer was rated as high in both chains.

The results obtained for the different dimensions of the NEP are according to a general orientation towards pro-ecological worldviews (New Ecological Paradigm), meaning that they do not believe that humans are superior to other all other species, that progress is an inherent part of human history, and that the Earth provides unlimited resources; thus, they are preferably characterized by a pro-NEP attitude and seem environmentally sensitive. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the scale with the lowest scores and highest standard deviation was "limits to growth", contrasting with the highest scores found in the scales "fragility of nature's balance" and "possibility of an ecocrisis". These results are aligned with other studies carried out in similar national and socioeconomic contexts (i.e [69], [70]); it must be considered that the higher scores are also related with sociocultural background of respondent, with higher education positively correlated with NEP scores [41], [71], [72]. Likewise, sociocultural background influences pro-environmental concepts attained by respondents [73]–[75], which could be a explanation for the perception of humans as being dominant over nature and consider nature to be powerful while at the same time recognising its limits and considering it as a fragile system that can be destroyed by humans, found in EU countries. This result can be explained as, on one hand, recognising the need to use nature for human purposes in situations where economic development needs resources and where it is therefore acceptable to abuse the environment in order to grow more quickly; while on the other hand, people are highly aware of the dangers caused by extensively abusing and polluting the environment.

Besides, according to the study carried out by Harraway [76], the tendency to recycle (reduce and reuse) can be related to Item 6 (“The earth has plenty of natural resources if we just learn how to develop them”); the tendency to conserve by Item 5 (Humans are severely abusing the environment) and Item 15 (“If things continue on their present course we will soon experience a major ecological catastrophe”.); the tendency to support animal (and plant) rights by Item 7 (Plants and animals have as much right as humans to exist) and Item 12 (Humans are meant to rule over the rest of nature) and the tendency to be cautious about the future by Item 4 (Human ingenuity will ensure that we do not make the earth unliveable) and Item 14 (Humans will eventually learn enough about how nature works to be able to control it. This approach of focusing on the implied behavioural intentions, or tendencies, of respondents builds upon the earlier work of Ajzen and Fishbein [77]) that emphasized that people do not need to make decisions about things, but do tend to consider how they will behave in relation to them; this may explain the inconsistencies between the results of the NEP, and those obtained by other environmental questionnaires, regarding specific behaviours and habits (recycling, sustainable mobility), as it has been already stated by different authors (i.e [78], [79]), suggesting the use of additional or alternative scales based on the “cost of behaviour” [72], [80]–[82].

Regarding the results of the workers awareness section, it is striking that the most valued options as a source of knowledge about what should and should not be recycled are media and internet and social networks, ahead of education and training. This might mean that further efforts must be made in education and training in order to improve the awareness and knowledge of how to correctly recycle. As for the most valued option to correctly separate has been “to reduce environmental pollution” followed by “for ethical choices and future generations”. In addition, the preferred role of the public administration in tackling the recycling problem has been to encourage citizens to separate the waste collected with payments/discounts on the bill and to provide sufficient infrastructure for recycling. On the other hand, fines have not been one of the most valued options; incentives are preferred to coercive attitudes.

As for the circular economy employees’ awareness, the 76% declared to know the concept of CE, which is a high rate. In further studies it would be analysed if the concept is correctly understood. Moreover, as shown by the results, consumer awareness will be a product of clear and direct messages that motivate them to shift their behaviour. The most effective way for consumers to shift to more circular behaviours in their consumption habits is to feel economically incentivized, for example with discounts or other incentives to return the packaging or rewards for using products or services efficiently.

Public administrations should foster the transition to more circular models through establishing a roadmap with concrete objectives which are ambitious and leverage the transformation of the model and engaging in a constant dialogue with companies to work along the same lines and to prevent regulation or deregulation from blocking or preventing the implementation of circular processes in companies.

11 LCC implementation (preliminary)

11.1 Results & conclusions: Agri-food chain

As it was performed in the LCA (see Deliverable D7.6) an eLCC assessment has been conducted on the agri-food case study, which is focused on utilizing waste streams from agri-food sector, specifically from lemon waste (peel and pulp).

The objective of this recycling process is to extract value from waste from its high value bioactive compounds, to produce new foods, nutraceuticals and cosmetics.

The eLCC model has been created on top of the LCA model, in order to assess the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the same input and output included in the LCA model³³. The next figure shows the same detailed flow chart used for the LCA.

Figure 30 Production chain of enzymatic extraction³⁴.

The following cost categories have been included in the demo:

- 1) physical input and output conventional costs (raw materials, energy, water, transport, waste management)
- 2) equipment costs

³³ For a more detailed description of the LCA model, please consult Deliverable D7.6.

³⁴ The flow chart is taken from Deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

- 3) installation costs
- 4) labour costs
- 5) maintenance costs

As it was done in the LCA, all the costs have been allocated between the 2 co-products, the fibre (solid phase) and phenolic extract (liquid phase):

- in those processes where both solid and liquid phases are present (tank and filtration), 75 % of the shared costs are allocated to the solid phase and 25 % to the liquid phase (dry mass allocation);
- costs related to the oven phase are entirely allocated to the solid phase,
- costs related to the concentration and lyophilization phases are entirely allocated to the liquid phase.

The following sections report the life cycle inventories (LCI) of all single processes included in this demo case.

11.1.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

As previously reported, the same input/out table used for the LCA has been integrated with the relevant costs, which cover the physical input, such as raw materials, water, energy and transport, as well as the physical output, such as condensed water which is treated as waste. The conventional costs related to each LCA input and output are described in Table 15.

Table 15. Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case eLCC

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
agri-food waste (lemon)	50	kg	45,66	Inbound transportation cost
enzyme	0,005	kg	0,15	
water (boiler feed water)	0,19	m3	0,76	
water (for extraction)	0,15	m3	0,60	
Electricity (total)	320,4	kWh	44,52	3 months average cost
<i>Electricity (for the tank)</i>	3,5	kWh	0,49	
<i>Electricity (for filtration)</i>	2,5	kWh	0,35	
<i>Electricity (for the oven)</i>	38,4	kWh	5,34	
<i>Electricity (for concentration)</i>	36	kWh	5,00	
<i>Electricity (for lyophilisation)</i>	240	kWh	33,35	
natural gas	6	m3	27,48	
Output	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
condensed water	0,08	m3	36	Waste management cost
carbon dioxide to air	11,13	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)
evaporated water	305,8	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)
Fiber (product)	3,6	kg	-	Recycling process output
Phenolic extract (product)	0,6	kg	-	Recycling process output

11.1.2 Equipment and installation costs

In order to process the input waste stream, no new equipment is needed. Therefore, no installation costs occur, while equipment costs include the yearly amortisation cost of the existing equipment that is used both for the recycling process, as well for other types of productions. To reflect the proper utilization of the equipment involved in the recycling process, the amortization costs have been allocated on the basis of the total yearly production (in mass), where the cost of the A2C project represents 32%, according to expert judgement from CTNC).

Table 16 reports, per each type of equipment, its amortization cost and the allocated cost to the recycled co-products.

Table 16 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case LCC

Input	Conventional Cost for the whole production (Amortization cost per year ³⁵) (EURO)	Conventional Cost for the recycled co-products production (Amortization cost per year) (EURO)
Tank	1450	464
Cutting and homogenising machine	8343	2669,76
Oven	930	297,60
Filtration equipment	1845	590,4
Freeze dryer/Lyophiliser	8134	2602,88

11.1.3 Labour costs

According to expert judgement from CTNC, to process 150 kg of lemon peel (from pre-treatment to purification and stabilisation, i.e. the whole process), it takes about 5 days x 8 hours/day x 3 persons, with an hourly cost of 20 €/h.

Since no further information was available, labour cost has been allocated 75% to the fibre and 25% to the phenolic extract.

11.1.4 Maintenance costs

Total yearly maintenance costs, for the equipment reported in the used in the process, sums up to 37,000 € per year, while the cost of the A2C project represents 32% (12,000€), according to expert judgement from CTNC. Maintenance cost include preventive and corrective costs.

Since no further information was available, maintenance cost has been allocated 75% to the fibre and 25% to the phenolic extract.

11.1.5 Waste management costs

The lemon waste recycling process does not produce any solid waste, but only condensed water (from the concentration phase), that needs to be treated as wastewater. Waste management cost therefore includes the cost of the treatment of condensed water, as already reported in Table 15. Since the concentration phase is entirely dedicated to the

³⁵ Amortization has been calculated over 8,33 years of use of each equipment. Only 32% of these equipment costs have been allocated to the lemon waste recycling process.

production of the phenolic extract, the wastewater treatment cost has been fully allocated to the phenolic extract.

11.1.6 Agri-food chain: total eLCC

The current paragraph reports the results of the whole recycling process and their co-products, fibre and phenolic extract, including the associated environmental costs, deriving from the application of the Delft University of Technology (see section 9.3.1) to the LCA results, with the details per cost category and per life cycle phase. For the environmental externalities, for alignment with the LCA results, only carbon footprint impact has been considered.

Table 17, Table 18, Figure 31 and Figure 32 show the results of the eLCC assessment of the production of 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste. From these tables and figures, it is evident that for both co-products, the total eLCC is driven by the conventional cost, which represents 99% of the overall costs for the fiber and 95% for the phenolic extract, whereas personnel costs and maintenance costs are the large contributors, followed by equipment costs.

Table 17. Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process - tank	Recycling process - filtration	Recycling process - oven	Waste management	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	-	-	0,10	0,07	1,48	-	1,66	0,5%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	5,73	-	-	-	5,73	1,8%
Equipment cost	-	22,25	3,87	4,92	3,31	-	34,34	10,7%
Maintenance cost	-	100,00	-	-	-	-	100,00	31,2%
Personnel cost	-	166,67	-	-	-	-	166,67	52,0%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,03	-	-	-	0,03	0,0%
Transport cost	9,51	-	-	-	-	-	9,51	3,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,28	-	-	-	0,28	0,1%
Total conventional cost	9,51	288,91	10,01	4,99	4,79	-	2,19	99,3%
Environmental costs	0,85	-	0,29	0,05	1,01	-	318,22	0,7%
Total eLCC	10,36	288,91	10,30	5,04	5,79	-	320,41	100%

Table 18. Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process - tank	Recycling process - filtration	Recycling process – concentration & lyophilisation	Waste management	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	-	-	0,20	0,14	63,92	-	64,27	6,6%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	11,45	-	-	-	11,45	1,2%
Equipment cost	-	44,50	7,73	9,84	173,53	-	235,59	24,3%
Maintenance cost	-	200,00	-	-	-	-	200,00	20,6%
Personnel cost	-	333,33	-	-	-	-	333,33	34,4%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,06	-	-	-	0,06	0,0%
Transport cost	19,03	-	-	-	-	-	19,03	2,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	-	-	60,00	60,00	6,2%
Water cost	-	-	0,57	-	-	-	0,57	0,1%
Total conventional cost	19,03	577,83	20,02	9,98	237,45	60,00	924,31	95,3%
Environmental costs	1,70	-	0,58	0,10	43,36	0,03	45,76	4,7%
Total eLCC	20,73	577,83	20,59	10,08	280,81	60,03	970,07	100%

Figure 31 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fiber from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Figure 32 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Focusing on the conventional costs, Figure 33 and Figure 34 clearly show the % contribution of each type of cost to the total conventional costs (the thickness of the arrow is proportional to its impact). For the fibre, Personnel cost represents more than 50% of the total conventional costs, while maintenance costs bring an additional 31%. For the phenolic extract the contribution of personnel and maintenance is still highly significant, but lower, being, respectively, 36% and 21%. For the phenolic extract, the cost of the concentration and lyophilisation equipment is significant as well, being 19% of the total conventional cost.

Figure 33 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of fiber from lemon waste (%)

Figure 34 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (%)

Personnel cost, as well as maintenance and equipment cost, are highly influenced by the demo testing small scale, which prevents the recycling process from achieving a high level

of efficiency. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis has been conducted to assess how the total cost would change if a higher scale and higher efficiency were applied. According to CTNC expert judgment, the current equipment set could treat up to 7500 kg of lemon waste input, instead of the 1250 kg assessed in the default scenario. Moreover, the increased efficiency could bring scale economy to personnel cost, as well as maintenance and equipment cost. Personnel hours, according to CTNC expert judgment, could be cut by 50%, dropping from the default 120 hours³⁶ per 150 kg of lemon waste input, to 60 hours to treat the same amount.

Table 19 reports the main assumption for the default and the alternative scenario assessed in the sensitivity analysis

Table 19. Default and alternative scenarios main assumptions – fiber and phenolic extract from lemon waste

Default scenario	Default scenario	Alternative scenario
Fiber & Phenolic extract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 120 hours of personnel per 150 kg of lemon waste input 1250 kg of lemon waste input yearly treated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 60 hours of personnel per 150 kg of lemon waste input 7500 kg of lemon waste input yearly treated

Figure 35 and Figure 36, and Table 20 and Table 21 show the results of the total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract. From the sensitivity analysis it is evident the considerable cost reduction for both co-products, as the fiber cost is reduced by 61% and the phenolic extract by 55%, thanks to a reduction in maintenance and equipment costs (-81%) and in personnel cost (-50%).

Figure 35 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - fiber from lemon waste - sensitivity analysis

³⁶ It was assumed that it takes about 5 days* 8 hours/day * 3 persons to treat 150 kg of lemon waste input.

Table 20 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	1,66	1,66	0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	5,73	5,73	0%
Equipment cost	34,34	5,72	-83%
Maintenance cost	100,00	16,67	-83%
Personnel cost	166,67	83,33	-50%
Raw materials cost	0,03	0,03	0%
Transport cost	9,51	9,51	0%
Water cost	0,28	0,28	0%
Total conventional cost	318,22	122,93	-61%
Environmental costs	2,19	2,19	0%
Total eLCC	320,41	125,13	-61%

Figure 36 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - phenolic extract from lemon waste - sensitivity analysis

Table 21. Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	64,27	64,27	0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	11,45	11,45	0%
Equipment cost	235,59	39,27	-83%

Maintenance cost	200,00	33,33	-83%
Personnel cost	333,33	166,67	-50%
Raw materials cost	0,06	0,06	0%
Transport cost	19,03	19,03	0%
Waste management cost	60,00	60,00	
Water cost	0,57	0,57	0%
Total conventional cost	924,31	394,64	-57%
Environmental costs	45,76	45,76	0%
Total eLCC	320,41	125,13	-55%

11.1.7 Agri-food recycled products vs conventional products

This section focuses on a possible comparison of the total eLCC assessment of the fibre and the phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste, against conventional (virgin) products that could be considered as alternative products already available.

Since the function of both the fibre and the phenolic extract is not yet fully defined, given that these substances can be included in a wide range of different formulations, the identification of possible benchmark products is still uncertain. For the phenolic extract, which is rich in antioxidant compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids), currently there is no proper reference product, since there is no nutritional claim on polyphenols or antioxidant capacity. In the LCA, some benchmark products have been investigated, as reported in the next table. Unfortunately, the conventional cost was not available for the whole list of products. On the contrary, for quercetin, only the conventional cost was provided (Table 22).

Table 22. Potential benchmark products for fiber and phenolic extract.

Agri-food recycled product	Benchmark product:	More information:	Scale:	Source:	Kg/CO ₂ emissions per kg of product ³⁷	Conventional cost (euro/kg)
Fiber from lemon waste	Inulin from root chicory	Root chicory is defined as an herbaceous plant with a fleshy taproot, and it is the main source of inulin. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre.	Industrial	Hingsamer et al. [83]	1,41	4,9/7
Phenolic extract from lemon waste	Antioxidant-rich powder extract from beet wastes	Ten different scenarios using beet root and leaf residues as inputs and five different extraction techniques. Used reference is pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) on beet leaves, for 1 g.	Laboratory	Arias et al.[84]	60	Not available
	Antioxidants from olive mill wastewater (OMW)	Three polyphenolic compounds recovered with liquid-liquid solvent extraction (three	Laboratory	Kalogerakis et al. [85]	13300	Not available

³⁷ Data from deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

	different solvents tested). Used reference is hydroxytyrosol extraction (0,247 kg from 1 m ³ OMW) with ethyl acetate solvent.					
Starch aerogel tablets containing vitamin E	Corn-based starch, aerogel preparation using supercritical carbon dioxide impregnation. Used reference the vitamin E (α -tocopherol, TOC) amount (15 mg) in a tablet (120 mg).	Industrial	De Marco et al. [86]	1687	Not available	
C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	Dataset name: "ascorbic acid production", location RER. LCIA results, EF v3.0.	Industrial	ecoinvent 3.8 database	2,9093	9,8	
Quercetin	antioxidant flavonoid present in onions	Industrial	CTNC expert judgement	Not available	28	

For this comparison, the environmental costs considered both for the conventional and the A2C product, are limited to the CO₂ equivalent emissions. Since for quercetin no LCA information was available, the comparison is purely based on the conventional cost.

Table 23 and Table 24, as well as Figure 37 and Figure 38, show the results of the comparison.

Table 23 A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – fiber from lemon waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost ³⁸	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon waste) – default scenario	318,22	0,46	318,67
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon waste) – optimized scenario	122,93	0,46	123,39
Conventional	Inulin from root chicory³⁹	7,44	0,08	7,52

³⁸ Only environmental externalities associated to CO₂ equivalent emissions have been included in the calculation.

³⁹ Organic inulin price is currently 7-10€/kg. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre (expert judgement from CTNC).

Figure 37 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Fiber from lemon waste

From the comparison, the cost of the fiber from lemon waste appears still significantly higher than the organic inulin.

Table 24. A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – phenolic extract from lemon waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost ⁴⁰	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – default scenario	924,31	9,09	933,40
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – optimized scenario	394,64	9,09	403,74
Conventional	C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	9,8	0,16	9,96
Conventional	Inulin from root chicory	28	n.a.	n.a.

n.a =not available

⁴⁰ Only environmental externalities associated to CO₂ equivalent emissions have been included in the calculation.

Figure 38 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Phenolic extract

With reference to the phenolic extract, the analysis shows that the total eLCC of the phenolic extract is still significantly high in comparison to the conventional product, such as ascorbic acid and quercetin (only conventional cost assessed). However, the uncertainty associated to the function of the phenolic extract, due to a wide range of possible final application, is very high and it affects the overall comparison

11.2 Results and conclusions. Plastic chain

As it was performed in the LCA (see Deliverable D7.6) an eLCC assessment has been conducted on the plastic chain case study, which is focused on upcycle plastic residues from the food sector to high added value products. The demo consists of recycling agricultural mulch film waste and waste from aseptic bags produced by the food industry, into new plastic pellet, which can substitute conventional LDPE virgin pellet, currently available on the market.

The eLCC model has been created on top of the LCA model, in order to assess the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the same input and output included in the LCA model⁴¹.

The comparison encompasses two types of pellets:

- a. Pellet blend which is 1/3 by weight made of the recycled LDPE and virgin calcium carbonate manufactured in the A2C project (hereafter referred to as A2C pellet) and 2/3 virgin LDPE pellet
- b. 100 % virgin LDPE pellet (conventional product)

The following cost categories have been included in the demo:

1. physical input and output conventional costs (raw materials, energy, water, transport, waste management)
2. equipment costs

⁴¹ For a more detailed description of the LCA model, please consult Deliverable D7.6.

3. installation costs
4. labour costs
5. maintenance costs

The following sections report the life cycle inventories (LCI) of all single processes included in this demo case.

11.2.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

As previously reported, the same input/out table used for the LCA has been integrated with the relevant costs, which cover the physical input, such as raw materials, water, energy and transport, as well as the physical output, such as soil and plastic sawdust which are treated as waste.

The conventional costs related to each LCA input and output are described in Table 25

Table 25. Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic chain demo case eLCC

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
agricultural mulch film waste	0,6282	kg	0,06	
calcium carbonate	0,01	kg	0,001	
polyelectrolyte chemical for water treatment	1,79E-04	kg	0,001	
calcium oxide	2,23E-03	kg	0,0005	
water	0,1208	kg	0,0004	
electricity	0,3635	kWh	0,058	
electricity from solar panel	0,03366	kWh	0	
diesel	6,43E-04	kg	0,0008	
Transport (agricultural mulch film waste)	0,6282 x 60	kgkm	0,00817	
Transport (calcium carbonate)	0,01 x 120	kgkm	0,00026	
Transport (polyelectrolyte)	1,79E-04 x 150	kgkm	0,00001	
Transport (calcium oxide)	2,23E-03 x 150	kgkm	0,00007	
Transport (diesel)	6,43E-04 x 50	kgkm	0,00001	
Output	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
soil	0,22	kg	0,002	Waste management cost
plastic sawdust	0,08	kg	0,0046	Wastewater treatment cost
Transport (soil)	0,22 x 40	kgkm	0,00191	
Transport (plastic sawdust)	0,08 x 94	kgkm	0,00163	
carbon dioxide to air	2,04E-03	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)
A2C pellet	0,3333	kg	-	Recycling process output

Since the final product is a pellet which is a mix of 1/3 of A2C recycled plastic pellet and 2/3 of virgin LDPE pellet, an additional cost of 1,5 euro per kg will be attached to the virgin LDPE pellet.

11.2.2 Equipment and installation costs

In order to process the input waste stream, 2 types of equipment are needed: a washing plant and an extruder, which are fully dedicated to the recycling process. Equipment costs include the installation costs as well as the yearly amortization cost which has been calculated considering a yearly production based on 12.000 t of input waste and 10 years life span (Table 26).

Table 26. Equipment life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic film demo case eLCC

Input	Conventional Cost for the whole production/recycling process (Amortization cost per year ⁴²) (EURO)
Washing plant	40500
Extruder	28700

11.2.3 Labour costs

According to expert judgement from GWC plastics, to get 1 t of recycled pellet (for cleaning/decontamination and recycling, i.e. the whole process), it takes about 1,5 hours, with an hourly cost of 86,63 €/h.

11.2.4 Maintenance costs

Total yearly maintenance costs, for the equipment reported in the use in the process, sums up to 131.508 € per year, with a yearly production based on 12.000 t of input waste.

11.2.5 Waste management costs

The agricultural film waste recycling process produces soil, as solid waste, and plastic sawdust, that needs to be treated as wastewater. Waste management cost therefore includes the cost of the treatment of both waste streams, as already reported in Table 25.

11.2.6 Plastic chain: total eLCC

The current paragraph reports the results of the whole recycling process and its product, the 33% recycled pellet, including the associated environmental costs, deriving from the application of the Delft University of Technology (see section 9.3.1) to the LCA results, with the details per cost category and per life cycle phase.

Table 27 and Figure 39 show the results of the eLCC assessment of the production of 1 kg of 33% recycled plastic pellet from recycled agricultural mulch film waste; these demonstrate

⁴² Amortization has been calculated over 10 years of use of each equipment.

that the total eLCC is driven by the conventional cost, which represents approximately 84% of the overall costs, whereas raw material cost is the largest contributor, followed by energy cost.

Table 27. Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of 33% recycled plastic pellet from recycled agricultural mulch film waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection	Transport	Raw materials	Energy	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process - equipment	Waste management	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	-	-	-	0,06	-	-	-	0,06	4,0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	-	0,00	-	-	-	0,00	0,1%
Equipment cost	-	-	-	-	-	0,01	-	0,01	0,5%
Maintenance cost	-	-	-	-	0,01	-	-	0,01	1,0%
Personnel cost	-	-	-	-	0,04	-	-	0,04	3,0%
Raw materials cost	0,06	-	1,00	-	-	-	0,00	1,07	74,0%
Transport cost	0,01	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,6%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,01	0,5%
Water cost	-	-	0,00	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,0%
Total conventional cost	0,07	0,00	1,00	0,06	0,06	0,01	0,01	1,20	83,6%
Environmental costs	0,00	0,00	0,20	0,03	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,24	16,4%
Total eLCC	0,07	0,00	1,20	0,09	0,06	0,01	0,01	1,44	100%

Figure 39 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of 33% recycled pellet from agricultural film waste (EURO/kg)

Focusing on the conventional costs, Figure 40 clearly shows the % contribution of each type of cost to the total conventional costs (the thickness of the arrow is proportional to its impact). The cost of virgin pellet represents 84% of the total conventional cost, followed by the agricultural mulch film waste transport cost (5,8%), electricity (4,8%) and personnel cost (3,5%).

Figure 40 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of 33% recycled pellet from agricultural film waste (%)

11.2.7 Plastic-film recycled products vs conventional products.

This section focuses on a possible comparison of the total eLCC assessment of the recycled pellet from agricultural film waste against the conventional (virgin) pellet that could be considered as an alternative product already available.

For this comparison, the environmental costs considered both for the conventional and the A2C product, include the full list of impact categories assessed according to the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method [13].

Table 28 and Figure 41 show the results of the comparison.

Table 28. A2C recycled product vs conventional product - total LCC – plastic pellet

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Plastic pellet (33% recycled content)	1,20	0,24	1,44
Conventional	Plastic pellet (100% virgin content)	1,5	0,30	1,80

Figure 41 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Plastic pellet

From the comparison, both environmental externalities costs and the conventional cost for the recycled pellet are lower than the virgin pellet ones. Therefore the total eLCC of the 33% recycled pellet is 20% lower than the 100% virgin pellet.

11.3 Limitations

Some methodological limitations should be considered when talking about Life-Cycle Costing and its application in the A2C project.

There is no standardised approach to conduct an eLCC analysis for products in the agrifood sector.

- No standards are available to conduct LCC for this sector (see section 9).
- The application of eLCC for food products and food waste streams seems to be recent and minimal, if compared to other sectors.
- Nevertheless, the methodological choices for conducting the eLCC in A2C have been described in the deliverable, so the approach is replicable.
- The cost of the conventional product, compared with the A2C recycled ones, are estimated on the average market price, by subtracting and estimated price mark up of 30%.
- The methodology to assess the environmental externalities is affected by uncertainty linked to the methods applied to estimate the damage associated with potential environmental impacts.

12 Conclusions

Transitioning to a CE requires a full systemic change, implying changes throughout value chains, from design to new business & market models, from new ways of treating waste to new ways of consumer behaviour, and innovation, not only in technologies, but also in organisations, society, finance methods and policies. A2C addresses these challenges going beyond traditional waste management, through a multidimensional approach, including citizens and all-relevant stakeholder in the process towards circularity. A2C addresses systematically all the factors hampering the implementation of circular solutions (socio-economic, environmental, policy & regulatory, financing).

Organisations are key actors in the transition towards sustainability and CE [38]. In order to successfully achieve the implementation of the A2C systemic solution, it is necessary to measure the social impact of the activities carried out within the project. This assessment will be made possible in further steps (D.7.9. Socioeconomic & sociocultural analysis report-Final) to estimate the social footprint of the A2C organisations and its potential contribution to the SDG. This information would be crucial to know if effectively the model developed in task 7.5 has been successfully adopted. Nevertheless, at this stage of screening, the results of the study have been a first sight to some metrics of the social footprint associated with the organisations activities and to estimate their scope in terms of the stakeholders affected. Moreover, this first exercise has allowed us to test the data gathering tools and to validate the selected indicators (both in terms of SO-LCA and in terms of awareness), making it easier to finetune the procedure for the next evaluation moment.

Likewise, regarding the economic evaluation, the eLCC approach has been selected and the results also demonstrate the validity of the selected indicators. Moreover, similar limitation has been found to those in the SO-LCA, namely the benchmarking with existing products or services and the need to scale up the processes to industrial level. It also must be highlighted that the methodology to assess the environmental externalities is affected by uncertainty linked to the methods applied to estimate the damage associated with potential environmental impacts. For both value chains (lemon waste & the plastic), the scale of the processes has a high influence on the costs, therefore in the final report (deliverable 7.9) a more adjusted evaluation will be performed on the demonstrators at industrial level.

Thus, once the project comes to its end, the assessment will provide more reliable information, with two main goals. On the one hand to raise A2C organisation's awareness on its own effects in the socio-economic field, and, on the other hand, to establish a number of measures to mitigate adverse impacts.

This will facilitate the adoption, replication, and long-term sustainability since the evaluation results will provide references and benchmarks that can be replicated in other products and national contexts.

13 References

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14 ANNEXES

14.1 Social Indicators Battery

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: WORKERS

Impact subcategory (I1): Forced labour

Employment terms (WQ1)	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the worker has agreed voluntarily the employment terms
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation-worker
Source	Methodological sheets

Forced Labour (W1)	
Definition	Forced or compulsory labour is any work or service that is exacted from any person under the menace of any penalty, and for which that person has not offered himself or herself voluntarily. Providing wages or other compensation to a worker does not necessarily indicate that the labour is not forced or compulsory. By right, labour should be offered voluntarily, and workers should be free to leave the employment at any time in accordance with established rules.
Calculation formula	N° of forced labour workers / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Impact subcategory (I2): Fair salary

Living wage per month (W2)	
Definition	Living Wage per month is defined as the income needed for a decent living, i. e. the monthly wage needed to cover the necessary living costs of an individual or family.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	€
Data source	INE
Level	Regional
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Minimum wage, per month (W3)	
Definition	Is the lowest gross wage a full-time worker can be remunerated in a specific country, defined by national law and legally binding
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	€
Data source	INE
Level	Regional
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Organisation average wage, per month (W4)

Definition	Organisation average wage provides information about the mean monthly salaries to assess if the salary is enough to afford a decent standard of living. The indicator is given as the mean of monthly earnings of all employees in the organisation in nominal terms.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	€
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified (D.7.5)</i>

Impact subcategory (I3): Working hours

Flexibility (WQ2)	
Definition	Employee's self-perceived quantification of the extent to which the company provides adequate flexibility for work-life balance, rest and overtime. The indicator provides a synthetic, albeit mainly subjective, measure of different dimensions involved in work-life balance
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale (1 to 6)
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5

Full-time staff (W5)	
Definition	Indicator to see the ratio of full-time permanent staff
Calculation formula	Full-time permanent staff / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Impact subcategory (I4): Equal opportunities/ discrimination

Gender equality (W6)	
Definition	This indicator is intended to measure the percentage of women in the total workforce
Calculation formula	N° of women / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Equal opportunities policies (W7)	
Definition	This indicator is intended to note the presence of policies aimed at promoting equal opportunities between men and women, such as for example a Gender Equality Plan
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I5): Health and Safety

Occupational safety measures (WQ3)	
Definition	Indicator to assess whether the worker perceives occupational health measures as adequate.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation - worker
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

Lost time injury frequency rate (W8)	
Definition	Lost time injury frequency rate, the number of lost time injuries occurring in a workplace per 1 million hours worked.
Calculation formula	N° of injuries x10 ⁶ / hours worked
Unit	[0, +∞]
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Presence of sufficient safety measures (W9)	
Definition	Occupational health and safety depend on the one hand, on the hazards and risks that workers are directly exposed to in their working environment. On the other hand, these occupational health risks can be limited by appropriate measures taken by the employer. This is assessed by the indicator “Presence of sufficient safety measures”.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	[0,1]
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Impact subcategory (I6): Social benefits, legal issues

Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations (W10.1-W10.2)	
Definition	Number of sanctions imposed for non-compliance with current regulations
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1} {0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Impact subcategory (I7): Workers’ rights (Freedom of association and collective bargaining)

Trade unions density (WQ4)	
Definition	This indicator serves to assess how liberal and vivid trade union culture is, and, in the end, to what degree the right to organize freely is assured in different sectors
Calculation formula	The trade union density rate is the share of employees who are union members, expressed as a percentage. Trade union membership excludes union members who are not in paid employment (self-employed, unemployed, retired, etc.). Number of persons members of a trade union / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Questionnaire

Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Collective Bargaining Agreement (W11.1, W11.2, W11.3, W11.4)	
Definition	All workers and employers have the right to establish and to join organisations of their choice, without prior authorization, to promote and defend their respective interests, and to negotiate collectively with other parties. They should be able to do this freely, without interference by other parties or the state, and should not be discriminated against because of union membership.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I8): Sexual harassment

Sexual harassment incidents reported (W12)	
Definition	This indicator verifies whether the company register the number of sexual harassments incidents.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{1,2} {0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS

Impact subcategory (I1): Fair competition

Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour (VC1.1- VC1.2)	
Definition	Presence of documented statement or procedures to prevent engaging in or being complicit in anti-competitive behaviour → not applicable → number of sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Impact subcategory (I2): Promoting social responsibility

Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (VC2)	
Definition	Accreditation of Corporate social responsibility compliance
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Suppliers audit (VC3)

Definition	Percentage of suppliers the enterprise has audited with regard to social responsibility in the last year
Calculation formula	Number of hired suppliers audited/ number of suppliers hired
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I4): Respect of intellectual property rights

Use of local intellectual property (VC5)	
Definition	This indicator is aimed to know if the company have had any type of conflict related with the use of intellectual property at local level
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I5): Wealth distribution

Fair price definition (VC6)	
Definition	Indicator to assess whether the price has been defined fairly: Definition of a fair price, i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin; this indicator can be either qualitative and quantitative, the latter calculated through a detailed cost assessment
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, 1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: SOCIETY

Impact subcategory (I1): Public commitment to sustainability issues

Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues (S1)	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has a public document as promise or agreement on sustainability issues. This information might be complemented with an interview
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, 1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I2): Contribution to economic development

Total taxation per capita (S2)	
Definition	Total taxes paid in the last year, by all typologies, per capita (organisation). Taxes paid represent a proxy for the social contribution of each company
Calculation formula	Taxation per capita= total taxes paid / total workforce
Unit	Euros
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation

Source	D.7.5 modified
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Impact subcategory (I3): Technology development

Technology transfer (S3)	
Definition	Involvement in technology transfer program or projects. The indicator verifies whether the company is actively involved in technology transfer programs or projects
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 modified

Investments in technology development/ transfer (S4)	
Definition	Share of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment. This indicator is a proxy for the effort made by the organisation in development and/or technology transfer, as well as the degree of technological innovation that a product incorporates
Calculation formula	$p_i = n_i/N_i$ p_i : proportion of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment items n_i : represents the investment in technology development and/or transfer (in euros) of the company N_i : represents the total investment, all items (in euros)
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 modified

Impact subcategory (I4): Corruption

Corruption (S5)	
Definition	This indicator assesses whether an organisation has implemented appropriate measures to prevent corruption
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I5): Poverty alleviation

Poverty alleviation programme (S6)	
Definition	The aim of the assessment is measuring the presence or not of proactive activities, such as strategies, action plans, investment, to reduce the poverty of the society
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: LOCAL COMMUNITY

Impact subcategory (I1): Access to material resources

Environmental management system (LC1)
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Definition	Presence of a certified environmental management system. The indicator verifies whether the company has a certified environmental management system.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 modified

Impact subcategory (I2): Access to immaterial resources

Community education initiatives (LC2)	
Definition	Community education initiatives fostered or promoted from the organisation (via their own funds or dedicated hours)
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I3): Delocalization and migration

Immigrant workforce rate (LC3)	
Definition	The immigration rate indicates social risks linked with a migrant inflow. The more migrants are in a certain region the more they influence the job market. Therefore, this indicator is intended to calculate the percentage of immigrants in the organisation workflow to be compared at regional level.
Calculation formula	Number of immigrants in the workforce/ total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 Modified

Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community (LC4)	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has any internal procedure for integrating migrant workers into the community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I4): Cultural heritage

Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage (LC5)	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has dedicated resources to promote the cultural heritage of the community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1 }
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I5): Safe and healthy living conditions

Promotion of community health (LC6)	
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Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has dedicated resources to promoting community health
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Impact subcategory (I6): Community engagement

Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation (LC7)	
Definition	To which extent the organisation has a diverse stakeholder's community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale 1-6
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

Number of meetings with community stakeholders (LC8)	
Definition	This indicator is intended to know whether the relationship of the organisation with its community stakeholders is recurrent
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP (<i>modified</i>)

Organisational support (volunteer-hours or financial) for community initiatives (LC9.1 – LC9.2)	
Definition	Organisations also foster community engagement through direct involvement in community initiatives and/ or through financial support of community projects. This indicator is intended to know whether the organisation supports community initiatives
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP (<i>modified</i>)

Impact subcategory (I7): Local employment

Workforce hired locally (LC10)	
Definition	Proportion of locally hired workers over total new hires. The indicator is a proxy of the organisations' involvement with the local workforce
Calculation formula	$p_i = n_i / N_i$ p_i : proportion of locally hired workers n_i : number of locally hired workers N_i : total workforce
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Spending on locally based suppliers (LC11)	
Definition	Proportion of spending on locally based suppliers over total expenditure on materials, equipment and services. The indicator is a proxy for the organisation's involvement

	with the local supply of goods & services, as well as for the weight of local suppliers in the manufacture of a product
Calculation formula	$p_i = n_i/N_i$ p_i : proportion of spending on locally-based suppliers of the company n_i : spending on locally-based suppliers (in euros) of the company N_i : total amount of spending on suppliers (in euros) of the company
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Impact subcategory (I8): Secure living conditions

Security complaints by the community (LC12)	
Definition	Number of legal complaints against the organisation with regard to security concerns by the local community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,+∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

STAKEHOLDER CATEGORY: CONSUMERS

Impact subcategory (I1): Health and Safety

Labelling (C1)	
Definition	Information available regarding features. The existence of labels in the product about its characteristics provides useful information to the consumer
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Consumer complaints (C2)	
Definition	Number of consumer complaints in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organisation
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System (C3)	
Definition	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I2): Feedback mechanism

Presence of consumers feedback mechanism (C4)	
Definition	Presence of a mechanism for consumers to provide feedback
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I3): Consumer privacy

Consumers complaints related to breach of privacy (C5)	
Definition	Number of consumer complaints related to breach of privacy or loss of data
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I4): Transparency

Organisation communication transparency (C6)	
Definition	Organisation effort on communication all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Impact subcategory (I5): End-of-life responsibility

Internal management systems (C7)	
Definition	This indicator is intended to know if the company has internal management systems that ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options for products. <i>In a product life cycle, end-of-life refers to product disposal, reuse, or recycling. In an environmental context, this concept is commonly referred to as extended producer responsibility. Product disposal can lead to significant environmental and social concerns.</i>
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

